

Faculty of Business & Humanities
Department of Sport & Early Childhood

The Impact of Physical Activity Interventions on Engagement and Responsiveness in Preschool Children

Master of Arts in Early Intervention and Inclusive Practice for
Children

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Student: **Kristna Rautek Potocnik**

Student ID: **K00326871**

Supervisor: **Dr. Helen Maher**

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Abstract

This dissertation explored how a physical activity intervention can influence engagement and responsiveness in preschool children within an inclusive learning environment. Early childhood is a critical stage for holistic development, where physical activity supports motor growth as well as social, emotional, and cognitive skills. Despite supportive policy frameworks in Ireland, including Aistear and Síolta, movement is often underused in preschool practice. This study aimed to investigate how a structured yet flexible intervention could enhance children's participation and inclusion.

The research followed a qualitative, participatory action research design grounded in an interpretivist and critical perspective. Two preschool classes, comprising of approximately 30–35 children aged between three and four-and-a-half years, and six educators participated. Data were collected through the researcher's reflective journal and semi-structured educator interviews before and after the intervention. The action research cycles of planning, implementing, observing, and reflecting ensured that activities were adapted continuously to meet children's needs while strengthening inclusive practice.

Findings showed that the intervention significantly improved engagement and responsiveness. Children displayed high levels of motivation and joy, often asking about "activity days" and creating their own games. Their ability to focus, follow instructions, and regulate emotions improved through structured play such as obstacle courses and group activities. Responsiveness to verbal and non-verbal cues also increased, with children mirroring gestures, reacting quickly to prompts, and supporting peers. These changes were particularly notable among children who were initially hesitant, highlighting the potential of inclusive physical activity to build confidence and resilience.

The role of educators emerged as central. In classrooms where teachers co-participated, modelled behaviour, and encouraged collaboration, children demonstrated greater progress in social and emotional domains. Limited adult involvement, by contrast, led to weaker outcomes. Reflective practice and

collaborative problem-solving supported educators in adapting activities to children's diverse needs and underlined the importance of professional development for embedding movement into inclusive pedagogy.

The study concluded that physical activity is more than a health recommendation; it is a powerful pedagogical tool for inclusion. By combining structure with flexibility, physical play promoted motor competence, engagement, responsiveness, and peer bonding. The findings align with existing literature and policy frameworks while also contributing new insights into the mechanisms through which movement fosters inclusion in early years education.

Although limited to a single preschool and short timeframe, this research offers valuable implications. It suggests that sustained educator participation, reflective practice, and adaptable activity design are essential for creating inclusive, movement-rich environments. Future studies should expand across multiple sites, capture children's perspectives more directly, and examine long-term outcomes.

In summary, this dissertation demonstrates that physical activity interventions can enhance engagement and responsiveness in preschool children. When educators act as co-participants and when activities are inclusive, enjoyable, and adaptable, children not only develop motor skills but also gain confidence, social connections, and a stronger sense of belonging. Physical activity therefore emerges as a vital pathway to inclusion, supporting holistic development and the rights of every child in early education.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context of Physical Activity in Early Childhood

Early childhood is a critical period of rapid growth where physical activity (PA) plays a central role in shaping children's holistic development. Movement during the preschool years supports not only physical health but also cognitive, emotional and social learning. The World Health Organization (2010) recommends that children under five engage in at least 180 minutes of physical activity each day, with a minimum of 60 minutes at moderate-to-vigorous intensity. These guidelines reflect strong evidence that active play contributes to the development of gross and fine motor skills, cardiovascular health, bone strength and lifelong habits of movement.

Beyond physical health, PA is closely linked to brain development and executive functioning. Research highlights that motor-rich environments stimulate neural connections and support skills such as attention, working memory and self-regulation (Diamond, 2000; Casey et al., 2005). These abilities are foundational for later academic learning, which shows that movement experiences in early childhood are not an optional addition but a core part of educational practice. For example, activities that involve balancing, jumping or sequencing movements challenge children's coordination while also encouraging persistence and problem-solving.

Emotional and social benefits of PA are equally significant. Active play allows children to express themselves, release tension and build resilience in managing emotions. Participation in group games promotes empathy, cooperation and peer bonding, which are vital for social inclusion and wellbeing (Wasenius et al., 2018). Physical activity also offers opportunities for imaginative and creative expression, enabling children to experiment with roles, narratives and collaborative problem-solving through movement.

Despite these benefits, international and national studies show a concerning decline in PA levels among young children. Many preschoolers spend large amounts of time in sedentary activities such as screen use, which contributes to rising rates of childhood obesity and reduced motor competence (Gunner et al., 2005; Hnatiuk et al.,

2012). Such trends underscore the importance of embedding PA opportunities early, before sedentary patterns become established.

Early years education provides a unique opportunity to reverse these patterns. Play-based and movement-rich environments encourage exploration, agency and independence, ensuring that children build both competence and confidence in physical activity. As Stuart (2021) argues, active play during the formative years strengthens the foundations for lifelong learning and wellbeing. By placing PA at the heart of early childhood education, practitioners can support the development of the “whole child” physically, cognitively, emotionally and socially at a stage when growth is most rapid and experiences are most influential.

In summary, physical activity during early childhood is far more than a health recommendation. It is a cornerstone of holistic development that supports the integration of body and mind, enabling children to thrive across all domains of learning and life.

1.2 The Irish Context and Policy Frameworks

In the Irish context, concerns about physical activity (PA) levels among children mirror international trends. Recent research shows that only 23% of primary school-aged children in Ireland achieve the recommended 60 minutes of daily moderate-to-vigorous activity (Woods et al., 2023). These findings highlight an urgent need to introduce healthy routines earlier, particularly in preschool, when children are still forming long-term habits of movement. The early years represent a unique opportunity to build a foundation for active lifestyles that can last throughout childhood and into adulthood.

National policy frameworks recognise this need and provide strong support for embedding PA into daily routines. Aistear (2024), Ireland’s early childhood curriculum framework, places play, movement and exploration at the centre of learning and development. It views physical activity as a means of promoting agency, wellbeing and participation for every child. Similarly, Síolta (Department of Education and Skills, 2017) sets quality standards that emphasise the importance of creating environments where children can be active, independent and socially engaged. Together, these

frameworks underline that PA should not be seen as a separate subject but as an integrated part of holistic education.

In addition, initiatives such as Move Well, Move Often (PDST, 2021) highlight practical strategies for supporting gross and fine motor development in early years and primary settings. These resources encourage educators to provide varied and inclusive activities that allow all children to participate meaningfully, regardless of their abilities or developmental profiles. The emphasis on adaptability and inclusion reflects a growing recognition that physical activity is also a social justice issue, as every child has the right to be active and to experience success in movement.

Despite these positive frameworks, challenges remain in practice. Many early childhood educators report limited training, restricted access to appropriate spaces and competing academic priorities that reduce the time available for movement-based activities (Oliver et al., 2007; Hesketh et al., 2017). This gap between policy and practice demonstrates that, while Ireland has strong curricular support for physical activity, more work is needed to ensure these principles are consistently implemented in everyday preschool environments.

1.3. Physical Activity and Inclusion

Physical activity (PA) is not only a way to promote health and development but also a powerful tool for inclusion in early childhood education. Inclusive practice ensures that all children, regardless of background, ability or developmental profile, can access meaningful learning experiences and participate fully in group life. PA naturally supports these goals because movement is universal and can be adapted to different needs, abilities and preferences.

In inclusive preschool settings, movement-based activities create opportunities for every child to experience success. Running, jumping, climbing or simple balance games can be modified so that each child participates at their own level. For example, a group game can allow some children to run, others to walk and others to copy movements while sitting. This flexibility helps to remove barriers and ensures that no child feels excluded from the activity. Such approaches are consistent with inclusive pedagogy, which views diversity as a resource for learning rather than a challenge (Florian and Black-Hawkins, 2011).

Physical activity also supports social inclusion by encouraging cooperation, empathy and peer interaction. Group games often involve turn-taking, sharing equipment and working together to achieve a goal. These experiences foster a sense of belonging and mutual support, especially for children who may struggle with communication or confidence. Research shows that adaptable PA programmes enhance engagement and peer bonding, helping children build friendships and resilience (Wasenius et al., 2018; Roth and Kriemler, 2015).

In addition, movement provides a non-verbal channel for expression, which is particularly valuable in inclusive contexts where some children may face language or sensory challenges. Through play and physical exploration, children can communicate emotions, negotiate roles and express creativity without relying solely on words. This not only broadens participation but also enriches the classroom culture by validating multiple ways of learning and interacting.

However, inclusion through PA does not happen automatically. Educators play a key role in planning activities that are flexible, supportive and meaningful for all children. Without adequate training and resources, opportunities for inclusive PA may be limited. Therefore, while PA has great potential to promote inclusion, realising this potential requires intentional practice, reflective planning and ongoing professional development.

1.4. Research Gaps and Rationale

Although research highlights many benefits of physical activity (PA) in early childhood, important gaps remain in understanding how PA interventions can be designed and sustained in inclusive preschool settings. Studies consistently show that PA supports motor competence, self-regulation and social participation (Grissmer et al., 2010; Costa et al., 2024), yet evidence of long-term effects is limited. Many interventions report positive short-term outcomes, but benefits often fade once structured programmes or external facilitators are removed (O’Byrne, Dinneen and Coppinger, 2023). This raises questions about how PA can be embedded into everyday routines in ways that are lasting and practical for educators.

Another gap concerns the specific focus on engagement and responsiveness. Engagement refers to a child’s ability to sustain interest, motivation and active

participation, while responsiveness reflects how children react to instructions, peers or new situations. Both are crucial indicators of learning, yet they are rarely measured directly in PA research. Most studies emphasise motor outcomes such as balance, strength or coordination, while less attention is given to how movement affects children's participation, social interaction and readiness to learn. As a result, little is known about the mechanisms through which PA fosters inclusion at the level of everyday classroom behaviours.

There is also limited exploration of children's perspectives. Research often relies on adult observations or educator reports, while children's own voices are rarely captured, especially those of children with developmental differences. Including children's perspectives could provide richer insights into what motivates them, what challenges they face and how they perceive inclusion during physical activities (Brown et al., 2022).

In addition, barriers to implementation remain underexplored. Many educators highlight challenges such as limited training, lack of space and competing curriculum demands (Hesketh et al., 2017; Mak et al., 2021). Although frameworks like Aistear and Síolta strongly promote movement and inclusion, translating these principles into practice is uneven across settings. More research is needed to understand how educators can be supported to confidently integrate PA into daily routines, especially in inclusive environments.

The rationale for this dissertation is therefore twofold: first, to address the gap in evidence about how PA interventions influence engagement and responsiveness in inclusive preschool contexts, and second, to provide practical insights into how educators can design sustainable, adaptable activities that benefit all children. By focusing on participation and inclusion rather than only physical outcomes, this study seeks to expand current understanding of PA as a tool for holistic development in early years education.

1.5. Research Question

The central focus of this dissertation is to explore how physical activity (PA) interventions influence children's participation in inclusive preschool environments. While many studies have measured outcomes such as motor competence or general

health, far less is known about the role of PA in shaping engagement and responsiveness, two key indicators of learning and inclusion. Engagement refers to a child's sustained involvement and motivation, while responsiveness captures how children react to instructions, peers and new experiences. To address this gap, the dissertation is guided by the following research question:

How does a physical exercise intervention affect the engagement and responsiveness of preschool children in an inclusive setting?

1.6. Significance of the Study

This dissertation holds significance on three interconnected levels: academic, practical and policy.

From an academic perspective, the study contributes new knowledge by linking physical activity (PA) interventions directly with engagement and responsiveness. Much of the existing literature concentrates on physical or health outcomes, such as improvements in motor competence, body mass index or general wellbeing (Barnett et al., 2008; Lum et al., 2022). While these outcomes are important, they do not capture the full impact of PA on everyday classroom participation. By focusing specifically on how children respond to cues and sustain involvement in inclusive group settings, this research provides fresh insights into the mechanisms through which PA supports holistic development and inclusion.

On a practical level, the study is valuable for early childhood educators who are seeking effective strategies to integrate PA into daily routines. Findings will highlight how structured yet adaptable interventions can enhance motivation, focus and peer cooperation in preschool classrooms. For practitioners who often face challenges such as limited space, restricted resources or uncertainty about how to adapt activities for diverse needs, the research offers evidence-based examples of how movement can be embedded into practice without requiring extensive additional resources. This makes the study directly relevant to everyday teaching and learning in inclusive early years settings.

At the policy level, the research supports national and international frameworks that promote movement, wellbeing and inclusion in early childhood. In Ireland, Aistear (2024) and Síolta (2017) emphasise the importance of play and physical activity,

while initiatives such as Move Well, Move Often (PDST, 2021) provide practical guidance for motor development. By showing how PA interventions can strengthen engagement and responsiveness, this study provides evidence that can help bridge the gap between policy intentions and classroom practice. It reinforces the idea that every child has the right to meaningful participation in active learning.

In summary, the significance of this study lies in its potential to inform theory, improve practice and strengthen policy. It demonstrates that PA is not only a matter of health but also a central component of inclusive pedagogy that promotes belonging, equity and holistic child development.

1.7. Structure of the Dissertation

The dissertation is organised into six main chapters, each designed to build a coherent and logical argument. Following this introduction, Chapter Two provides a comprehensive literature review, which examines theoretical foundations, key benefits, and challenges of physical activity (PA) in early childhood, with a particular emphasis on inclusive education. Chapter Three explains the methodology, outlining the qualitative action research design, sampling process, ethical considerations, and methods of data collection and analysis. Chapter Four presents the findings, structured around key themes that emerged from educator interviews, reflective journals, and classroom observations. Chapter Five offers a discussion of these findings, connecting them to existing research and theoretical perspectives while highlighting implications for practice. Finally, Chapter Six concludes the dissertation by summarising the main contributions, recognising limitations, and offering recommendations for educators, policymakers, and future research. This structure ensures clarity, consistency, and alignment with the study's central research question.

1.8. Conclusion

In conclusion, physical activity in early childhood must be understood as more than exercise or a health guideline. It is a foundation for holistic learning that shapes children's physical, cognitive, emotional, and social development. Despite strong evidence and supportive frameworks in Ireland, barriers remain in practice, particularly in relation to inclusion. This dissertation seeks to address these challenges by exploring how a physical activity intervention can strengthen

engagement and responsiveness in preschool children. By combining theory, practice, and policy, the study aims to demonstrate that movement is not only beneficial but essential for building inclusive, child-centred learning environments.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction to the Literature Review

Physical activity (PA) in early childhood is recognised as a cornerstone of holistic development, supporting physical growth, cognitive skills, social connections, and emotional wellbeing (World Health Organization, 2010; Stuart, 2021). The early years are a sensitive period when motor skills, social behaviours, and cognitive functions rapidly develop. Movement-rich environments stimulate brain growth, promote emotional regulation, and strengthen executive functions such as attention, planning, and problem-solving (Diamond, 2000; Casey et al., 2005).

Despite this importance, research shows a decline in PA levels among young children, alongside rising obesity rates and sedentary behaviours (Gunner et al., 2005; Hnatiuk et al., 2012). In Ireland, only 23% of primary school children meet the recommended 60 minutes of daily moderate-to-vigorous activity (Woods et al., 2023), highlighting the urgency of early, effective interventions.

Policy frameworks such as Aistear (2024) and Síolta (Department of Education and Skills, 2017) emphasise embedding PA into preschool routines to promote children's agency, exploration, and wellbeing. These frameworks support child-led, play-based learning, positioning movement as a fundamental pillar of early education rather than an optional extra.

Physical activity is also increasingly linked to inclusion. Inclusive education ensures all children, regardless of ability, background, or developmental profile, can access meaningful learning and actively participate (Sharma et al., 2008; Reynolds, 2001). Adaptable, developmentally appropriate PA interventions promote inclusion by enabling children to develop motor skills, build friendships, express themselves, and experience success alongside peers (Wasenius et al., 2018; Roth and Kriemler, 2015).

However, implementing effective, inclusive PA programmes faces challenges. Educators often encounter barriers such as limited training, restricted space, and competing academic priorities (Oliver et al., 2007; Hesketh et al., 2017). Sustained professional development, accessible resources, and supportive environments are

essential for confidently integrating PA into early childhood curricula (Duff, 2018; Mak et al., 2021).

Evidence-based interventions show positive short-term impacts on motor competence and engagement (Costa et al., 2024; Lum et al., 2022), but concerns remain about sustaining these benefits long term. Increased focus is being placed on designing inclusive, adaptable approaches embedded in everyday practice to ensure lasting developmental gains and equitable participation (Pate et al., 2016; Brown et al., 2022).

This literature review critically examines the theoretical foundations, benefits, implementation strategies, and challenges of promoting PA in inclusive early childhood settings. It identifies key research gaps and explores opportunities for creating sustainable, movement-rich environments that uphold every child's right to active, meaningful learning.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

A strong theoretical foundation is essential for understanding why and how physical activity (PA) supports holistic child development in early years education. This section outlines the key concepts that underpin the integration of movement into preschool learning environments, drawing on both developmental theory and practical frameworks.

Preschool teachers increasingly recognise PA as vital for cognitive, social, emotional, and physical growth (Senol, 2021). Movement-based experiences build coordination, self-regulation, and executive functioning skills essential for learning and everyday life. Yet, many early childhood settings face barriers such as limited space or rigid scheduling, which reduce opportunities for physical engagement.

Despite well-documented benefits, PA levels in young children remain low. In Ireland, only 23% of primary school children achieve the recommended 60 minutes of daily moderate-to-vigorous activity (Woods et al., 2023), highlighting the need for intentional, theory-informed approaches to embedding movement in early education.

Play-based learning, promoted by national curriculum frameworks like Aistear (2024), offers a strong pedagogical basis for integrating movement into daily routines.

Rooted in constructivist theory, it fosters exploration, autonomy, and experiential learning—principles that align closely with physical engagement. Through active play, children not only develop motor skills but also learn problem-solving, cooperation, and creative expression.

Viewing these practical strategies through a theoretical lens enables educators to embed PA more intentionally and inclusively. The following sections (2.2.1 to 2.2.4) examine inclusive education, motor development theories, social-cognitive perspectives, and inclusive pedagogy, each contributing to a comprehensive understanding of movement in early childhood learning.

2.2.1 Inclusive Education

Inclusive education ensures that all children, regardless of abilities or circumstances, have access to meaningful, high-quality learning experiences (Sharma et al., 2008). In Ireland, there is growing momentum toward educational environments that support equal participation for all learners (Reynolds, 2001). Inclusion goes beyond placing children with developmental difficulties in mainstream settings—it is about enabling every child to reach their potential through shared, engaging, and responsive experiences (Mikas and Roudi, 2012; Zuckermann, 2016).

Its principles are rooted in a societal commitment to diversity, equity, and participation (Bricker, 1995; Zrilić and Brzoja, 2013). Early reformers such as Itard and Montessori demonstrated the learning potential of children with disabilities when provided with appropriate support. Contemporary inclusive pedagogy builds on this by emphasising adaptation, flexibility, and active engagement for all children (Roberts and Callaghan, 2021).

Children’s developmental needs vary widely, including intellectual disabilities, autism, motor and sensory impairments, chronic illnesses, behavioural challenges, and exceptional abilities requiring enrichment (Zrilić, 2011; Dizdarević, 2014). These needs may stem from biological, environmental, hereditary, or socio-economic factors such as poverty, which can significantly shape early development (Bouillet, 2010). Effective inclusion therefore requires flexible, context-sensitive educational responses.

Integrated early years settings create environments where all children can interact, play, and learn together (Karamatić-Brčić, 2011; Kobescak, 2000). Research shows that inclusion benefits all children—supporting empathy, cooperation, and emotional intelligence from an early age (Minou, 2011; Bouillet, 2010).

However, achieving genuine inclusion remains challenging. Barriers such as insufficient teacher training, limited resources, and persistent bias still hinder progress (Dizdarević, 2014). Building supportive environments that foster belonging is key to ensuring meaningful participation for every child (Moore, 2015).

Inclusive practice must also extend to physical activity. Movement-based activities provide natural opportunities for participation, self-expression, social interaction, and success, particularly when adaptable and inclusive. Research indicates that real-world and fine motor activities in daily routines (e.g., bead-threading, building, cooking) enhance both motor competence and confidence (Suggate et al., 2023; Walsh, 2020).

This close connection between inclusive education and physical development underpins the exploration of motor development theories in the following section.

2.2.2 Theories of Motor Development in Early Childhood

Understanding motor development through a theoretical lens enables educators to design meaningful, responsive physical activity experiences that meet children's developmental needs. Several key theories explain how motor skills emerge and how physical activity can support this process in the early years.

The Maturation Theory (Gesell, 1928) suggests that motor development follows a biologically pre-determined sequence, with skills emerging as the nervous system matures. Physical activity supports but does not accelerate this timeline, highlighting the need to respect individual readiness and avoid premature pressure.

By contrast, the Dynamic Systems Theory (Thelen, 1989) views motor development as the product of interaction between biological, environmental, and cognitive systems. Development is non-linear and shaped by individual experiences. Purposeful activities, such as climbing, balancing, or cooperative games, stimulate sensory, muscular, and cognitive systems, enhancing skill acquisition.

The Ecological Theory (Gibson, 1979) emphasises the child’s active role in exploring their environment. Motor skills develop through perceiving affordances, opportunities for action, in surroundings. Natural play spaces such as playgrounds, sandpits, and uneven terrain allow children to experiment, adjust, and refine movement through exploration.

Together, these perspectives show that early childhood is a critical window for developing motor competence. Physical activity during this time supports brain development, executive functioning, and long-term health (Stuart, 2021; Oliver et al., 2007). Yet nearly half of preschool-aged children fail to achieve the recommended 60 minutes of daily activity (Tucker, 2008), underscoring the need for structured, developmentally appropriate interventions.

Research by Jones and Okely (2020) stresses integrating physical activity from infancy to build lifelong movement habits. The “Growing Up in Ireland” study found that gross motor competence at age three depends not only on biological maturation but also on play environment quality and caregiver interaction , supporting the role of environmental and social inputs (Williams et al. 2013).

The Demonstration Project on In-school and Early Years Therapy Support (2020) puts these theories into practice through structured daily activities such as “Superman” and “Crab” positions, which target balance, bilateral coordination, and postural strength—key school readiness skills. Such activities show how theory can inform inclusive, play-based interventions that promote both physical and cognitive growth.

These theories collectively provide a robust foundation for designing interventions that are developmentally sensitive, adaptable, and responsive to each child’s context, reinforcing that movement is essential for holistic learning in early childhood.

2.2.3 Social-Cognitive and Play-Based Learning Theories

Social-cognitive and play-based theories explain how children acquire motor, cognitive, and social skills through interaction, observation, and play. They highlight the role of social environments and guided participation in supporting development through physical activity (PA).

Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977) states that children learn by observing and imitating others, especially peers and adults. In group PA, they model behaviours such as turn-taking, cooperation, and encouragement. When educators demonstrate movements or join in physical play, they provide learning opportunities that extend beyond motor skills to socio-emotional growth.

Similarly, Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978) emphasises learning through social interaction. His concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), what a child can do independently versus with help, applies directly to PA. In physical play, educators and skilled peers can scaffold learning by guiding new skills, such as balancing or participating in cooperative games.

Piaget (1962) also recognised play as central to early learning. Through both structured and unstructured play, children experiment, solve problems, and build autonomy. Physical play offers natural contexts for refining motor skills, developing spatial awareness, and navigating social relationships. Educators enhance this by offering varied, developmentally appropriate equipment and open-ended movement opportunities.

Other approaches reinforce learning through movement and interaction. The Reflective Practitioner model (Schön, 1983; Vujičić et al., 2018) shows how educators improve practice by reflecting during and after activities. Dynamic Systems Theory (Thelen, 1989) and Ecological Theory (Gibson, 1979) stress that development emerges from interactions between the child, environment, and materials, supporting flexible activities and adult involvement.

These perspectives affirm that play is a primary medium for learning, including physical learning particularly in inclusive settings, where social modelling and guided participation benefit children with diverse needs. Grissmer et al. (2010) found fine motor competence at school entry strongly predicts later academic success, underscoring the value of embedding tasks like drawing, cutting, and manipulating objects into daily routines. Combining physical play with social interaction and scaffolded learning creates developmentally supportive, inclusive environments for all children.

2.2.4 Inclusive Pedagogy in Early Childhood

Inclusive pedagogy is an approach to teaching all children together rather than separating by ability (Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011). It views diversity as a resource for learning and promotes three principles: valuing diversity, ensuring equitable participation, and maintaining high yet realistic expectations.

In early years PA contexts, this means designing movement activities that allow meaningful participation for all children. Tasks are naturally adaptable—for example, in a group game, some may run, others walk, or mimic movements from a seated position. Educators can adjust activities through simplified instructions, visual or tactile prompts, peer modelling, and team-based goals.

Wasenius et al. (2023) found adaptable movement-based activities improve engagement for children with diverse needs. The Demonstration Project on In-school and Early Years Therapy Support (2020) offers practical examples, such as altering equipment size, changing activity pace, or adding cues to make PA accessible.

Group-based PA that emphasises collaboration over competition fosters belonging, social connection, and emotional safety. This approach not only develops motor skills but also empathy, cooperation, and resilience, reinforcing the message that every child has the right and ability to move, play, and grow alongside peers.

2.2.5 Summary of Theoretical Perspectives

A strong theoretical base explains why PA is vital in early childhood education, especially in inclusive settings. Vygotsky's ZPD (1978) shows how guided support helps children build skills and confidence. Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977) highlights learning through observation and imitation, while Piaget's Constructivist Theory (1962) links active play to problem-solving and sensory learning.

Inclusive Pedagogy promotes teaching all children together by adapting environments rather than children (Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011). The Reflective Practitioner model (Schön, 1983) encourages continuous improvement through reflection. Dynamic Systems Theory (Thelen, 1989) and Ecological Theory (Gibson, 1979) stress the interplay of body, environment, and experience, while the Universal

Design for Learning framework (PDST, 2021) supports participation through multiple means.

Neuroscience research connects PA to brain development, showing links to attention, emotional regulation, and memory (Diamond, 2000; Stuart, 2021). Together, these theories show that movement is not just about fitness. It supports cognitive, emotional, and social growth. Educators who apply these perspectives can create inclusive, movement-rich environments where all children can thrive.

2.3 The Importance of Physical Exercise in Early Childhood

Physical activity is fundamental to early childhood development, supporting children's physical health, cognitive growth, social skills, and emotional regulation (World Health Organization, 2010; Bowles et al., 2017). Despite this recognised importance, numerous studies report a concerning decline in activity levels during the early years, coinciding with rising rates of childhood obesity and sedentary behaviours (Gunner et al., 2005). While guidelines recommend at least 180 minutes of physical activity daily, only a small percentage of young children meet these targets, and much of the activity performed is of low intensity (Goldfield et al., 2012; Hnatiuk et al., 2012).

Socioeconomic inequalities further compound these challenges. Children from disadvantaged backgrounds often face limited access to safe play areas, fewer opportunities for structured physical activity, and a higher risk of obesity and inactivity (Ministry of Health, 2014, 2015). Rural children tend to be more active than their urban peers, illustrating the influence of environmental context (Woods et al., 2023). National frameworks such as Aistear (2024) emphasise the importance of creating inclusive learning environments that promote movement, agency, and participation for all children.

Recent studies have challenged assumptions about children with developmental difficulties. Kolehmainen et al. (2023) found that, with appropriate support, these children can meet international physical activity guidelines, reinforcing the need to maintain high expectations and avoid limiting opportunities based on disability. This finding aligns with inclusive pedagogical principles that advocate flexibility and equity in access to physical experiences.

The home environment and parental engagement are also highly influential. Parents shape children's activity habits through modelling, encouragement, and the structuring of daily routines (Li et al., 2015). Brown et al. (2022) and Fináncz et al. (2023) argue that early interventions should extend beyond physical activity and nutrition to incorporate social and emotional wellbeing within a comprehensive approach to child development.

Educators hold a pivotal role in this process. Lum et al. (2022) emphasise that professional development and clear leadership in physical activity promotion are essential for increasing participation in early years settings. Similarly, Tonge et al. (2017) found that educator–child interactions directly influence children's willingness to engage in physical activity, particularly when activities are meaningful, enjoyable, and supported through positive reinforcement.

A systematic review by Hesketh et al. (2017) highlighted that children's physical activity is shaped by a complex web of factors, ranging from individual motivation and family practices to the availability of safe outdoor spaces and institutional priorities. Using a socio-ecological lens, the authors argue that promoting movement in early childhood requires a multi-tiered approach that addresses personal, interpersonal, community, and policy levels.

In summary, fostering physical activity in early childhood must be understood as a collective responsibility shared by families, educators, and policy-makers. Inclusive strategies that acknowledge the interplay between environmental, social, and individual factors are essential to ensuring every child's right to a healthy, active start in life.

2.3.1 Physical Activity and Motor Skill Development

A substantial body of evidence supports the strong link between physical activity (PA) and motor skill development in early childhood. More active children generally show better coordination and movement proficiency (Barnett et al., 2008), while low motor competence in the early years is associated with later sedentary behaviour and reduced confidence in physical participation (Barnett et al., 2009; Wrotniak et al., 2006). Early development of gross motor skills: running, jumping, throwing and fine

motor skills: grasping, manipulating small objects are essential for daily functioning and school readiness (Berk, 2013; Ridgway et al., 2009).

Both structured and unstructured play contribute to motor development, particularly when they involve tasks challenging coordination, sequencing, and balance. Obstacle courses, ball games, and climbing activities support agility, postural control, and confidence (Cork & Kerry OT Team, n.d.). Systematic reviews confirm that targeted gross and fine motor programmes, delivered by trained educators in early years settings, can lead to sustained improvements (Strooband et al., 2020; Veldman, Jones & Okely, 2016).

Longitudinal studies show that early PA enhances not only motor skills but also cognitive and social outcomes. Gains in motor competence are linked to improvements in executive functioning, academic achievement, and social participation (Grissmer et al., 2010). Xing and Wu, (2025) found these benefits are maintained when programmes are consistent and age-appropriate. From an inclusion perspective, PA offers adaptable opportunities, musical movement, sensory-rich games, cooperative play that allow all children to experience success and enjoyment (Mak, Chan & Capio, 2021).

2.3.2 Early Motor Development and Later Outcomes

Early motor development influences physical, cognitive, social, and emotional trajectories. Children who develop motor skills early are more likely to participate in sports and PA later in life: fostering social inclusion, confidence, and academic engagement (Ridgway et al., 2009). Butcher and Eaton (1989) also found that different types of play foster different competencies, supporting the value of variety in physical experiences.

The Dynamic Systems Theory (Wasenius & Thelen, 2003) explains that motor development results from interactions between biological readiness, environmental stimuli, and experience. This aligns with Adolph and Berger's (2005) finding that cultural practices shape milestone achievement, and with Foster and Hartigan's (2006) argument for using developmental rather than chronological age, especially for premature children, when planning interventions.

Motor milestones are closely linked with other developmental domains. Colson and Dworkin (1997) found strong links between early motor and language skills, while Eichner-Seitz, Pate & Paul (2023) reaffirmed the influence of social, biological, and cultural factors. Grissmer et al. (2010) concluded that fine motor skills at school entry are among the strongest predictors of later academic achievement. These findings highlight the need to treat motor skill support as a developmental priority, especially for children with diverse needs.

2.3.3 Cultural and Developmental Considerations

Motor development is shaped by cultural practices, developmental history, and environmental context. Adolph and Berger (2005) show that caregiving norms such as infant carrying and opportunities for free movement affect balance and coordination. In educational settings, Foster and Hartigan (2006) stress using developmental age as a guide, particularly in inclusive classrooms with varied developmental profiles.

Motor development is interconnected with cognitive and language growth (Colson & Dworkin, 1997; Diamond, 2000; Piek et al., 2008). Practical strategies, such as occupational therapy-informed movements (“chair leg lifts,” “snake curls”), can improve bilateral coordination and vestibular function, enhancing attention and working memory (le Roux, 2022). Embedding such tasks into daily routines provides inclusive ways to support multiple developmental domains.

2.3.4 Impact of Physical Activity on Health and Cognitive Outcomes

PA in early childhood contributes to both immediate health and long-term development. Structured movement programmes enhance motor competence (Alpert et al., 1990) and can reduce BMI (Mo-suwan et al., 1998), while inactivity increases health risks (Moore et al., 1995). Benefits extend to executive functions such as attention, self-regulation, and planning (Diamond, 2000; Casey et al., 2005; Holt & Mikati, 2011).

However, intervention results vary. The Mighty Moves programme, a 10-week curriculum implemented in preschool settings to develop fundamental movement skills such as running, hopping, throwing, and balancing through structured, play-

based activities, improved motor proficiency but did not significantly increase overall physical activity levels or reduce BMI in participating children (Bellows & Anderson, 2013). The mixed results highlight that gains in skill competence do not automatically translate into higher daily activity, as home environments, socioeconomic circumstances, and broader policy supports play a crucial role in sustaining behavioural change. Complementing these findings, neuroscience evidence shows that motor-rich experiences can drive neuroplasticity and enhance behavioural regulation (Halperin et al., 2012). In conjunction with also promoting growth in brain regions associated with memory and learning (Chaddock-Heyman et al., 2015), underscoring the potential of early, skill-focused interventions when embedded within supportive multi-level systems.

PA also supports perception, helping children interpret and respond to their environment (Kaiser, 2021; Krishna, 2012). Active exploration: running, climbing, dancing which develops focus, balance, and body awareness (Cahen & Tacca, 2013). Meta-analysis shows daily PA enhances visual perception and thinking skills with notable benefits for children with coordination challenges (Vestberg et al., 2017). Sensory-rich environments with music, outdoor play, and fine motor tasks are especially valuable between ages 3–6 (Thompson & Strosser, 2012; Solum et al., 2020; Tamblyn et al., 2022).

Movement with peers promotes cooperation, turn-taking, and self-expression, while regular activity improves self-regulation (Xue et al., 2019) and school readiness. Though much research focuses on older children, evidence suggests daily PA can enhance perceptual and cognitive development in preschoolers (Bidzan-Bluma & Lipowska, 2018; Wang et al., 2022).

Taken together, these findings provide compelling support for embedding active play and movement-based learning into early education. PA in preschool is not only a health imperative but also a strategy for cognitive enrichment, emotional regulation, and inclusive participation.

2.3.5 Evidence-Based Physical Activity Interventions in Early Childhood

Evidence consistently shows that structured physical activity (PA) in early childhood delivers meaningful developmental benefits, including improved motor competence,

physical fitness, and overall wellbeing. While programme formats vary, successful initiatives typically share key features: strong educator involvement, active family engagement, developmental alignment, and operation within supportive policy frameworks.

Programmes such as Jumping Beans (Pigou, 2013), Hip-Hop to Health Jr. (Fitzgibbon et al., 2005), and Germany's PAKT trial (Roth & Kriemler, 2015) demonstrate that daily, teacher-led PA sessions can significantly enhance motor skills in preschool-aged children. These benefits are amplified when parental components, such as movement-based "homework" and educational workshops, reinforce consistent messages and active participation at home.

Recent approaches emphasise starting physical engagement from infancy. Eichner-Seitz, Pate & Paul (2023) highlight the developmental value of "tummy time" and unrestricted floor movement during early caregiving, which lay essential foundations for later motor, cognitive, and socio-emotional development.

Community-based models show how PA can be embedded in broader family and social contexts. New Zealand's Green Prescription Active Families programme (Wood & Johnson, 2013) achieved sustained behaviour change through wraparound support and community involvement. Similarly, Portugal's Super Quinas project (Costa et al., 2024) found that even small increases in structured PA, such as one weekly extracurricular session, can improve motor competence, aerobic fitness, and sleep quality.

In Ireland, programmes like the Active School Flag (ASF), which helps schools include more daily movement and physical activity, and Project Spraoi, which encourages children to be active and eat healthier, have shown good results in primary schools. Schools with the ASF report that pupils are more active every day (Woods et al., 2010; Bowles et al., 2017), while Project Spraoi has improved children's activity levels, eating habits, and overall wellbeing (O'Byrne et al., 2023). Both programmes work well because schools are committed, teachers plan together, and activities link physical activity with healthy eating and mental health.

Despite these successes, global disparities remain. Howells & Sääkslahti (2019) note that the World Health Organization has not established standardised guidelines for

children under five, and national recommendations vary widely in clarity and implementation.

Overall, the literature indicates that the most effective interventions are developmentally sensitive, multi-dimensional, and supported by collaboration between educators, families, and communities. For such models to be implemented and sustained, particularly in Ireland, ongoing investment in professional development, institutional resources, and parental outreach is essential. Embedding PA as a core component of early education, rather than an optional extra can help ensure all children, regardless of background or ability to develop physical competence, confidence and lifelong healthy habits.

2.3.6 Gaps and Challenges in Practice

Despite strong evidence supporting physical activity (PA) in early childhood, several persistent barriers limit its consistent and meaningful implementation. A key challenge is the absence of unified, evidence-based guidelines tailored specifically to preschool-aged children. While general recommendations exist (Timmons et al., 2007), ambiguity regarding age-appropriate intensity, frequency, and types of movement creates uncertainty in practice.

Educational priorities also play a role. As Oliver et al. (2007) note, early years settings often prioritise cognitive and literacy-based learning, reducing time and resources for movement-based activities. This imbalance undermines the holistic approach promoted by Aistear, which positions play and physical engagement as central to learning.

Policy inconsistencies further complicate matters. Although national strategies support PA, their translation into daily practice varies widely. McLachlan (2015) highlights that local interpretation often leads to significant differences between institutions, weakening systemic impact. A widespread lack of educator training adds to the problem, with many practitioners reporting low confidence and limited skills in designing inclusive, developmentally appropriate movement experiences (Hesketh et al., 2015).

Sustainability is another concern. O'Byrne, Dinneen & Coppinger (2023) found that while external facilitators can temporarily boost PA engagement, these gains diminish

once facilitators withdraw. Their “step-back” model revealed that without ongoing mentoring or structural reinforcement, PA levels decline, indicating that short-term interventions without long-term infrastructure are insufficient.

These issues reflect broader systemic disconnects between research and practice; policy and implementation; training and expectations. Addressing them requires a multi-layered approach combining educator upskilling, supportive leadership, clear policy guidance, and stronger family and community involvement.

To embed PA as a core component of early education, it must be viewed not as an optional extra but as a fundamental right and necessity for every child. This shift demands both resources and a cultural realignment within early years education, one that fully embraces the developmental power of movement.

2.4 Engagement and Responsiveness in Preschool Children

Engagement and responsiveness are key indicators of how young children experience and participate in learning, particularly within early childhood education and care (ECEC) settings (Aistear, 2024; Haugland et al., 2024). Engagement refers to sustained interest, motivation, and emotional involvement, encompassing behaviours such as focus, persistence, and active contribution (Costa et al., 2024). Responsiveness reflects how children react to instructions, sensory stimuli, or social interactions, expressed through language, gestures, facial expressions, or movement (Sámi ECEC study, 2022; Kipping et al., 2024).

Theoretical models conceptualise engagement as a multidimensional construct involving behavioural, emotional, and cognitive domains (Laevers, 2005; Aistear, 2024). Understanding these dimensions helps educators assess not only whether a child is participating but the depth of their involvement. Responsiveness provides insight into a child’s readiness to interact and learn, making it a valuable marker of developmental progress.

Tools such as the Leuven Involvement Scale (Laevers, 2005) offer structured ways to observe engagement, while teacher reports and checklists are often used to evaluate responsiveness (Haugland et al., 2024). These assessments help identify children who may need additional support and inform inclusive teaching strategies.

Recent research by Melillo et al. (2023) shows that targeted physical interventions to reduce retained primitive reflexes (RPRs) can improve brain connectivity and cognitive performance in children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Reducing RPRs, linked to delayed cortical maturation and motor challenges, enhances motor readiness, enabling children to follow instructions and sustain attention more effectively. The study also found increased interhemispheric connectivity and reduced abnormal lateralisation, which are associated with more efficient information processing and better responsiveness to verbal and non-verbal cues. Such outcomes support the view that PA interventions can act as catalysts for improved social communication, emotional regulation, and participation in inclusive preschool environments.

In inclusive settings, engagement serves as a marker of equitable participation for children with diverse developmental profiles (Aistear, 2024; Haugland et al., 2024). Higher engagement correlates with better academic outcomes, richer social interactions, and stronger emotional wellbeing (Costa et al., 2024; Sámi ECEC study, 2022). By observing and responding to individual cues, educators can adjust their approaches to create more responsive learning environments.

PA interventions are effective in enhancing both engagement and responsiveness. Staff-led movement sessions, especially when supported by professional development, improve motor coordination, object control, participation, and enthusiasm (Haugland et al., 2024). The Super Quinas programme illustrates how weekly PA sessions can improve not only fitness and sleep but also engagement in group routines and Doberstein structured play (Costa et al., 2024). Research by Purbasari et al. (2020), and (2013) further shows that structured, repetitive activities build children's confidence, engagement, and task participation, while consistent routines reduce anxiety and promote active involvement.

Nature-based approaches provide additional benefits. The Sámi ECEC study (2022) found that regular outdoor experiences support physical and mental health, encourage exploration, and foster peer interaction. These findings highlight the potential of natural environments to promote holistic development through unstructured yet purposeful play.

However, not all interventions achieve sustained results. For example, NAPSACC UK reduced children's lunchtime energy intake but did not significantly increase total

daily PA within ECEC settings (Kipping et al., 2024). Similarly, despite higher participation in school sports initiatives, overall PA among Irish children remains below recommended levels (Woods et al., 2023; Harrington et al., 2022). These outcomes suggest that structural, cultural, and curricular barriers can limit programme impact.

The Aistear framework (2024) advocates for integrated, play-based pedagogies that embed PA into daily routines and promote children's agency. Creating environments that facilitate movement, exploration, and child-led engagement is essential for fostering development and inclusion.

In summary, enhancing engagement and responsiveness in early childhood requires more than simply providing activities. It calls for intentional, inclusive, and developmentally sensitive practice. Programmes that combine PA with responsive pedagogy, supported by educator training and outdoor access, are most likely to create environments where all children thrive socially, emotionally, and physically (Haugland et al., 2024; Aistear, 2024; Sámi ECEC study, 2022).

2.5 Physical Exercise Interventions in Inclusive Preschool Settings

Physical activity (PA) is essential for early childhood development, supporting motor skills, social interaction, self-regulation, and learning engagement (Timmons, Naylor & Pfeiffer, 2007; Martyniuk & Tucker, 2014). WHO (2019) recommends at least 180 minutes of daily PA for preschoolers, yet many do not meet this target, with MVPA often averaging only 1.5–1.8 minutes per hour (Timmons, Naylor & Pfeiffer, 2007). Low activity levels are linked to environmental constraints, limited equipment, and lack of adult-led opportunities (Bower et al., 2008).

Educators play a critical role in increasing PA through active participation, encouragement, and structured planning (Martyniuk & Tucker, 2014; Tonge et al., 2019). Barriers such as limited training and confidence can be addressed through targeted professional development (Ward et al., 2010). Integrated approaches combining movement with cognitive and social activities improve physical, communicative, and cooperative skills (Vazou and Mavilidi, 2021; Lum et al., 2022; Roth & Kriemler et al., 2015). Programmes like PAKT show that teacher-led sessions

embedded in daily routines can boost motor competence without major extra resources (Roth & Kriemler et al., 2015).

Melillo et al. (2023) demonstrate that reducing retained primitive reflexes (RPRs) via targeted movement enhances brain connectivity, attention, and responsiveness, especially in children with ASD. These gains remove physical barriers to participation, promote shared activities, and support emotional regulation. Improved responsiveness fosters positive peer interaction, adaptability, and a sense of belonging.

Umbrella reviews confirm that structured delivery, educator involvement, and well-designed environments are key to success (Lum et al., 2022). Stuart (2021) and Oliver et al. (2007) recommend up to three hours of PA daily for optimal outcomes. Super Quinas (Costa et al., 2024) shows that even weekly sessions can improve motor competence, fitness and sleep. Activities such as balancing, crawling, and jumping support motor control and peer relationships (Meštrović et al., 2011; Rimmer & Rowland, 2008), especially when matched to developmental stages (Petrić, 2022).

Sustaining equitable PA requires national and local strategies (Woods et al., 2023; Harrington et al., 2022). Frameworks like Síolta (Department of Education and Skills, 2017) and the Irish Move Well, Move Often resource (PDST, 2021) guide inclusive design using the TREE framework: Teaching, Rules, Equipment, Environment. Croatian initiatives also show benefits of kinaesthetic and sport-based programmes for motor skills, motivation, and participation (Šuknaić, 2018; Ušković, 2022).

In summary effective inclusive PA interventions are structured, developmentally responsive, and embedded in supportive environments. Success depends on educator training, adaptive planning, and collaboration to ensure all children benefit from movement.

2.5.1 Types of Movement-Based Interventions

Movement-based interventions in early childhood vary in structure, from brief daily routines to targeted programmes led by trained facilitators. Activities include play-based motor skills, sensory-motor integration, music-and-movement, and outdoor exploration, balancing structured guidance with child-led movement for autonomy and engagement. Resources such as the DIPPE framework (2022) and Special

Olympics fitness guides (The Inclusion Club, 2022) offer inclusive strategies for motor, sensory, and communication needs. Ruiz-Esteban et al. (2020) found structured physical education improved preschoolers' coordination more than unstructured play, highlighting the value of guided approaches.

2.5.2 Key Outcomes and Success Factors

Effective interventions improve motor competence, attention, emotional regulation, social interaction, and classroom engagement, with pronounced benefits for children with developmental challenges. Success factors include visual cues, clear verbal guidance, positive feedback, and adaptable activities. Educator training and reflective practice sustain inclusive delivery, while Lum et al. (2022) emphasise consistent educator involvement for lasting developmental gains.

2.5.3 Challenges and Barriers in Implementation

Barriers include limited time due to academic demands, lack of staff confidence, insufficient resources, and physical space or safety restrictions (Skočić Mihić, 2011; Hesketh et al., 2017). Older children with motor delays may face low confidence or fatigue; the Older Child Resource Pack (NHS, n.d.) recommends breaking tasks into manageable steps. In Ireland, Aistear, Síolta, and PDST's Move Well, Move Often (Department of Education and Skills, 2017; PDST, 2021) promote UDL and the TREE model for adaptive, inclusive practice. Croatian studies show the value of interdisciplinary work with physiotherapists and occupational therapists, and of imaginative movement or simplified sports for improving coordination, wellbeing, and peer interaction (Šuknaić, 2018). Overcoming barriers requires systemic support through professional development, intentional planning, and collaboration among educators and allied professionals to ensure equitable access to PA benefits (PDST, 2021; Department of Education and Skills, 2017).

2.5.4 Sensory Integration in Inclusive Practice

Sensory integration is the neurological process enabling children to interpret and respond to sensory input to support movement, regulation, and learning (Ayres, 2002). In early childhood, this includes internal senses such as vestibular (balance)

and proprioceptive (body awareness) and external inputs like touch, sound, and vision (Biel & Peske, 2007).

Children with autism or sensory processing differences may have atypical responses that affect posture, focus, regulation, and group participation, limiting access to physical activity without adaptations. Evidence shows that structured sensory-based movement such as: tactile exploration, deep pressure, and rhythmic vestibular activities like swinging, can improve attention, self-regulation and inclusion.

Embedding these strategies into daily routines helps children feel secure, confident and ready to engage with peers.

Frameworks such as Aistear and Síolta call for environments responsive to the whole child, while UDL promotes barrier removal through personalised choice and environmental adaptation (PDST, 2021). Incorporating varied textures, sound levels, or movement intensity into activities can boost participation in group contexts.

Internationally, a Croatian study reported gains in coordination, sensory regulation, and peer interaction following sensory-focused movement programmes for children with processing challenges (Pajk Kraljević & Podhraski, 2023). Though from a different context, these principles apply to Irish inclusive practice.

Sensory integration should be embedded in physical activity planning, ensuring all children—not only those with diagnosed needs—can access learning and social interaction equitably.

2.6 Educators' Perspectives and Role in Physical Activity Interventions

Early childhood educators are central to embedding physical activity (PA) in preschool learning, yet their perspectives are often underrepresented in intervention design. The success of PA initiatives depends largely on educators' confidence, motivation, and ability to deliver inclusive and developmentally appropriate opportunities (Buckler & Bredin, 2021).

While Aistear and Síolta promote integrated movement, implementation varies. Many educators feel underprepared to lead structured PA, particularly in developing motor skills or adapting activities for diverse needs (Oliver et al., 2007; Buckler & Bredin, 2021). Barriers include limited time, space, equipment, rigid schedules, and competing curricular demands, with a focus on literacy often sidelining physical

development despite its role in regulation, executive function, and social skills (Suggate et al., 2023; Stuart, 2021).

Inclusive practice can be especially challenging. Educators working with children with developmental delays or disabilities report needing more training to adapt movement-based activities (Conderman & Johnston-Rodriguez, 2009). Effective inclusion requires pedagogical skill and emotional resilience (Bouillet, 2008). Professional development is the key for ongoing practice-focused training with mentoring, peer learning and coaching which increases confidence and fidelity (Duff, 2018). One-off workshops rarely lead to sustained change; reflective, embedded approaches have greater impact.

Despite initiatives like Get Ireland Active and the Active School Flag, early years educators have less support than primary teachers (Department of Health, 2016). Many lack clear, practical tools for integrating movement into daily pedagogy. Interventions led solely by external facilitators often yield short-term gains, but without building educator capacity, change is rarely lasting (O'Byrne et al., 2023).

Empowering educators to design and adapt PA in their own settings fosters ownership and responsiveness to individual needs which is an essential step in creating inclusive, movement-rich environments where all children can thrive.

2.7 Gaps in the Existing Literature

Although inclusive physical activity (PA) in early childhood is increasingly recognised as vital, several gaps remain. Addressing these is essential for designing sustainable, developmentally responsive interventions.

A major gap is the limited inclusion of children's own perspectives. Most studies focus on adult observations, with few engaging children directly, particularly those with developmental difficulties. Including children's voices, as Brown et al. (2022) argue, could reveal motivations and barriers, ensuring interventions are genuinely child-centred.

Another limitation is the generalisation of inclusion strategies. Many programmes promote diversity but lack differentiation for specific developmental profiles. Uniform models often overlook distinct motor, sensory, and social-emotional challenges faced by children with disabilities, limiting effectiveness (Plazibat, 2018).

Environmental and adult-related barriers are also underexplored. Over-cautious supervision and limited access to well-designed spaces can reduce autonomy and discourage exploration. Hesketh et al. (2017) note that adult risk perception can undermine PA programmes and limit children's confidence in physical risk-taking.

Longitudinal evidence is scarce. Most research emphasises short-term gains, such as motor coordination and peer interaction, without assessing whether benefits last. Studies like the PAKT trial in Germany and Pate et al. (2016) suggest sustained PA throughout the preschool day supports moderate-to-vigorous activity levels, but such examples are limited in scope.

Systemic continuity is another challenge. Many programmes focus on initial inclusion but reduce structured PA once basic milestones are reached, risking stagnation or regression (Plazibat, 2018). The Intervention Program Study (2023) highlights that PA should be combined with good nutrition and sleep for long-term wellbeing, yet multi-domain integration remains rare.

Finally, while professional development is recognised as key, few studies examine how training impacts educator confidence, planning, and long-term commitment. Evidence shows that one-off workshops are insufficient. Instead sustained and reflective training is needed to embed PA in daily practice (Buckler & Bredin, 2021).

Future research should prioritise children's perspectives, develop individualised strategies that address internal and environmental barriers, evaluate long-term outcomes, and ensure educators receive ongoing support to maintain inclusive, movement-rich learning environments.

2.8 Summary

This literature review examined how physical activity (PA) supports children's development in early childhood, with emphasis on inclusive settings. PA enhances motor skills, cognition, emotional regulation, and social interaction (World Health Organization, 2010; Diamond, 2000; Grissmer et al., 2010). Early childhood is a critical period for embedding movement into daily routines, with benefits that can extend into later life (Ridgway et al., 2009; Pate et al., 2016).

Inclusive PA interventions enable all children, regardless of ability, to participate, explore, and build relationships (Aistear, 2024; Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011).

When well-planned, they foster belonging, development, and reduced inequality (Wasenius et al., 2018; Roth & Kriemler, 2015). Play-based approaches that value child agency and social learning are particularly effective (PDST, 2021; Demonstration Project, 2020).

The review highlights key theoretical foundations. Social Learning Theory and Sociocultural Theory show the role of observation, imitation, and guided interaction. The Reflective Practitioner model (Schön, 1983) supports ongoing educator development, while Dynamic Systems Theory (Thelen, 1989) and Ecological Theory (Gibson, 1979) emphasise learning through interaction with people, spaces, and materials.

Challenges remain. Educators often lack training, and settings face constraints such as time, resources, and competing academic priorities (Oliver et al., 2007; Hesketh et al., 2017; Buckler & Bredin, 2021). Despite supportive frameworks like Aistear and Síolta, a gap persists between policy and practice (Department of Education and Skills, 2017).

Research gaps include limited inclusion of children's perspectives, insufficient adaptation for diverse developmental needs, and a lack of longitudinal studies (Plazibat, 2018; Brown et al., 2022; Hesketh et al., 2017). Long-term evidence, such as Roth & Kriemler (2015), shows benefits can be sustained if support continues.

Educators are central to effective implementation. With the right training, resources, and policy alignment, they can create movement-rich environments where every child feels included (Duff, 2018; O'Byrne, Dinneen & Coppinger, 2023; Buckler & Bredin, 2021).

In summary, placing PA at the heart of early childhood education requires investment in educator capacity, stronger policy–practice links, and long-term, inclusive research which ensures all children can thrive through movement, play, and meaningful participation.

3. Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter explains the methods used in the study called The Impact of Physical Activity Interventions on Engagement and Responsiveness in Preschool Children.

The study looked at the question: How does a physical exercise intervention affect the engagement and responsiveness of preschool children in an inclusive setting?

The research used a qualitative, action research method, based on an interpretivist view. This means it focused on understanding how people's experiences and social interactions shape knowledge, instead of looking for one fixed truth.

In recent years, education research has moved away from thinking that knowledge is always objective and the same for everyone. At present, it is understood that knowledge is connected to social relationships and depends on the situation (O'Toole, 2022). This study also used a critical approach, looking at how power, culture, and relationships can influence education.

3.2 Research Philosophy and Approach

This study is based on the interpretivist view, which says that knowledge is created by people through their experiences and the situations they are in. This study is based on the interpretivist perspective, which views knowledge as being created by people through their experiences and the situations in which they live. Schwandt (1994) explains that interpretivism holds reality not as fixed but as socially constructed, meaning that people understand the world differently depending on their background, context, and relationships. Interpretivism does not believe there is only one true reality. Instead, it says there are many realities, each shaped by people's own experiences and interactions. This matches the aim of this research, which is to understand how preschool children and their teachers experience a physical exercise intervention.

The study also includes a critical view. This means it looks at how power, society, and politics can affect education. A critical view understands that traditional research often ignores the voices of teachers and participants. By using Participant Action

Research (PAR), this study makes teachers and children active partners in the research. They help to design and change the activities based on their own experiences (O'Toole, 2022).

3.3 Research Design

This study used an action research design because it allows the activities to be checked and improved all the time, based on the needs of the participants. Action research works well in early childhood education, where flexibility and quick responses are important. It helps to understand deeply how both children and teachers experience the intervention. The process follows a cycle of planning, action, observation, and reflection. This cycle makes it possible to make small changes to improve the activities and make them more inclusive (McCombes, 2023).

Kemmis and McTaggart describe action research as a group, self-reflective process done by participants to improve their practice and understanding. Their spiral model of planning, action, observation, and reflection gives a strong but flexible structure. This matches the changing needs of inclusive early years education (1988).

In line with Participant Action Research (PAR), teachers in this study were not only participants but co-researchers. Their knowledge, experiences, and reflections were important for building understanding and improving activities (O'Toole, 2022).

Each cycle started with planning the physical activities, then doing them with the children. The children's engagement and responses were carefully observed and recorded. The researcher and teachers then reflected on what happened and used this to make changes for the next cycle. This kept the intervention child-focused and inclusive at all times.

The study also included reflective meetings with teachers, as suggested by Tobin, Farren and Crotty (2024). These meetings encouraged open discussion and supported professional learning. The research built on trust between the researcher, teachers, and children, following a relational pedagogy approach, which sees strong relationships as the key to engagement and real participation (Skehill and O'Donovan, 2024).

3.4 Population and Sampling

This study used purposive sampling to choose participants. The group comprised of two classes totaling about 30–35 preschool children aged between 3 and 4.5 years, and 6 teachers who worked with these children every day. The participants were chosen using clear inclusion and exclusion rules to make sure they matched the aims of the research. Children were included if they were enrolled in the preschool taking part in the study and if their parents or guardians gave written consent.

Teachers were included if they worked directly with the children every day and if they agreed to join the study as co-researchers. All participants came from one preschool known for its strong inclusive education practice.

3.5 Participation Process

The participation was organised together with the preschool management. First, a meeting was held with the teachers to explain the aims, steps, and ethical rules of the study. Parents and guardians were informed through a detailed letter, which explained the purpose of the research, what participation would involve, and the ethical safeguards. Consent forms were included with the letter so they could read and decide at home (Appendix A)

Teachers were invited to join the study during the meeting, where they could ask questions, talk about the process, and were also given a consent form (Appendix B).

Participation was completely voluntary, and no payment or reward was given. Everyone was told they could leave the study at any time without any problems or negative effects.

Ethical rules were followed at all times. This included making sure the information was clear, that consent was freely given, and that the children's assent was asked in a way they could understand (Appendix C). Recruitment continued until the right number of participants was reached. The group consisted of girls aged between 3 and 4.5 years, some with additional needs and some without, which supported the aim of making the study inclusive.

3.6 Data Collection Methods

The data for this study came from two main sources: a reflective journal kept by the researcher during the entire programme, and semi-structured interviews with the educators before and after the intervention (Appendix D).

The reflective journal was written after each session while the researcher was delivering the programme. It included detailed notes about what happened during the activities, how the children responded, which aspects worked well, and what changes might be needed. These reflections helped to improve the sessions while they were taking place and also gave important insights for the final analysis.

The interviews with educators before the intervention explored their views about children's engagement, responsiveness, and the role of physical activity in an inclusive preschool environment. The interviews after the intervention focused on any changes they observed in the children, their opinions about the activities, and their reflections on the overall process. Each interview lasted about twenty minutes and was audio-recorded with the permission of the participants (Appendix D).

The interview questions were prepared using ideas from existing research and were checked in advance to make sure they were clear and relevant to the preschool context. All audio recordings were stored securely on a password-protected device. The transcripts used pseudonyms (E1-E6) instead of real names, and all personal details were removed. In line with the policies of the Technological University of the Shannon, the data will be securely stored for seven years and then permanently deleted (TUS Dissertation Handbook, 2024).

3.7 Trustworthiness and Limitations

Ensuring the trustworthiness of this study was very important because it used a qualitative and action research approach. Several strategies were used to make the findings more reliable. The researcher spent extended time with the participants, which helped to build trust with the children and educators and allowed for a deeper understanding of their behaviours and responses.

Different sources of information were combined, including the reflective journal and the interviews with educators. This triangulation added depth to the findings and

supported their credibility. Regular reflective meetings with educators allowed different perspectives to be shared and included in the interpretation of the results. Discussions with the research supervisor also provided valuable feedback and helped to reduce possible bias from the researcher.

Dependability was supported by keeping clear records of all research procedures, decisions, and changes made during the study. A reflexive approach was used, with the researcher recording personal thoughts and possible biases in the reflective journal to make the analysis more transparent.

The study setting, participants, activities, and data collection process were described in detail to help others decide if the findings could be applied in a different context.

There were some limitations. The research took place in only one preschool with a small number of participants, which means the results cannot be generalised to all settings. The researcher had the dual role of delivering the programme and collecting data, which might have introduced bias, although efforts were made to reduce this through reflexivity and triangulation. The young age of the children made it difficult to gather direct verbal feedback, so the analysis relied on the observations of the researcher and the views of the educators. The time limits of a Master's dissertation meant that it was not possible to track the long-term effects of the programme.

Even with these limitations, the study provides important insights into how physical activity can support engagement and inclusive practice in early childhood education, and it highlights areas for future research.

3.8 Ethical Considerations

Ethical principles were an essential part of the planning, delivery, and reporting of this research, especially because it involved young children and their families. Ethical approval was granted by the Research Ethics Committee at the Technological University of the Shannon after the researcher submitted a detailed application explaining all planned procedures and safeguarding measures (Appendix E).

The study followed key ethical principles such as respect for each person, beneficence, non-maleficence, justice, and honesty. Written informed consent was obtained from the parents or guardians of all participating children. The children's assent was also sought using age-appropriate communication, such as clear verbal

explanations and simple visual supports (Appendix C), to make sure they understood that they could choose to take part or not. They were also told that they could withdraw at any time without any negative consequences.

Confidentiality and anonymity were protected by using pseudonyms instead of real names and by removing all identifying information from transcripts and notes. All data was stored securely on an encrypted and password-protected device, with access only for the researcher. The study followed all Technological University of the Shannon data protection policies and the General Data Protection Regulation. The data will be stored securely for seven years and then permanently deleted. (TUS Dissertation Handbook, 2024)

The activities in the programme were designed to be inclusive, enjoyable, and suitable for the children's developmental levels, with minimal risk. The researcher paid close attention to the children's emotional wellbeing during each session. If any sign of distress or discomfort appeared, the activity was stopped immediately and the child's welfare was prioritised above the research goals.

Ethical practice also included creating a supportive atmosphere for families, recognising that some parents may experience emotional challenges related to their child's development (Ljubešić, 2014). The study respected the voices of both educators and children, following Lundy's Model of Participation, which ensures that children have space, voice, audience, and influence in matters that affect them (2007).

The approach taken in this research matched the principles of national frameworks such as Aistear (2024) and the international standards of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989), placing the rights, dignity, and wellbeing of each child at the centre of the process.

3.9 Pilot Study

A short pilot study was carried out before the main data collection began. The main purpose of the pilot was to help the children and the researcher become familiar with each other, to build trust, and to create a comfortable research environment. It also allowed the educators to see the style and structure of the planned intervention sessions.

The pilot study was not focused on formally testing the research tools. Instead, it aimed to observe the children's initial reactions in a relaxed and supportive situation. During the pilot, the researcher noted that having clear routines, using visual supports, and keeping a playful and flexible approach helped to keep the children engaged.

Based on what was learned during the pilot, small changes were made to the plan for the main intervention. These changes included giving the children more choice in activities and making transitions between tasks smoother.

The pilot study was important because it helped to make sure that the activities were safe, suitable, and realistic for the children. It also helped the researcher, educators, and children to feel more comfortable and prepared for the main study, which increased the quality and relevance of the data collected.

3.10 Researcher Positionality and Reflexivity

Because this study followed an interpretivist approach, the researcher's position and reflections were recognised as an important part of the process. The researcher is an Early Years Professional with experience working with children who have additional needs. This background, knowledge, and personal beliefs could influence how the researcher interacted with participants and how the data was interpreted.

To reduce bias and keep the findings connected to the participants' real experiences, the researcher used reflexive journaling throughout the study. After each session, the researcher wrote personal reflections, emotional reactions, and notes about possible assumptions. This helped the researcher to remain aware of personal influence on the process and to make conscious efforts to focus on the participants' voices.

The study also followed a praxeological approach, which means that it valued shared decision-making and respected the agency of both children and educators. The researcher aimed to share power with the participants as much as possible, seeing them as partners in the research process. This approach helped to create a respectful and collaborative environment where participants felt their contributions were valued.

By keeping a reflexive stance, the researcher was able to better understand how personal perspectives might shape the study and take steps to ensure that the

findings were based on the authentic experiences of the participants rather than solely on the researcher's own views.

3.11 Summary of Methodological Challenges

During the research process, several methodological challenges appeared. One challenge was balancing the two roles of the researcher, as both the person delivering the programme and the person collecting the data. This created the possibility of bias, although careful reflection and the use of different data sources helped to reduce this risk.

Another challenge was the natural variation in the children's engagement from day to day. Factors such as mood, health, or events outside the preschool could influence how the children took part in the activities. This meant that the researcher needed to remain flexible and adjust the sessions when necessary.

To address these challenges, the researcher used reflective practice and regular discussions with the educators. This allowed for changes to be made in a way that respected both the needs of the participants and the goals of the research. By being adaptable, the study remained true to its inclusive and participatory aims, even when unexpected difficulties occurred.

3.12 Conclusion

This chapter described the research methodology used in the study, including the research philosophy, design, sampling strategy, recruitment process, data collection and analysis methods, ethical considerations, and measures taken to ensure trustworthiness. It also discussed the researcher's positionality, the challenges faced during the process, and the steps taken to address these challenges.

By using an action research approach within an interpretivist and critical framework, the study was able to explore in a collaborative and flexible way how physical exercise interventions influence engagement and responsiveness in an inclusive preschool setting. The involvement of educators as co-researchers and the use of reflective practice ensured that the intervention remained child-focused and responsive to participants' needs.

The study placed a strong emphasis on ethical practice, reflexivity, and methodological rigour. It aimed to provide useful insights into inclusive practice that supports the participation and wellbeing of young children. The next chapter will present the findings that came from the thematic analysis of the collected data.

4. Findings

To protect confidentiality, the educators' real names were replaced with pseudonyms and are referred to as E1, E2, E3, E4, E5, and E6 throughout the findings. The following sections present the key themes that emerged from the data, showing how educators and children experienced the physical exercise intervention in the inclusive preschool setting.

Theme 1: Child Engagement and Responsiveness

1.1 Active Participation

Children actively participated in planned and spontaneous movement-based activities, showing growing anticipation, enthusiasm, and autonomy.

Data from observations and educator reflections consistently revealed high levels of engagement during physical sessions. Structured activities, such as obstacle courses and games in the school hall, became a regular part of the children's routine. Educators noted that "every Tuesday and Thursday, we have access to the primary school hall" (E1), and children "loved the activities", often asking "Is it activity day today?" (E2, E3, E4). This repeated anticipation highlights the establishment of a motivational routine.

Some children who had previously been hesitant began joining with increased confidence and joy. As E1 observed, "Some children who were usually hesitant started participating more freely and with more enthusiasm." Educators also began offering more autonomy: "I've started planning activities that give children more freedom to explore movement on their own terms" (E6). This shift supported self-directed creation, as shown when "children built their own obstacle course using available materials" (journal).

The consistent engagement suggests that embedding movement into the daily routine supported children's active participation. Novelty, routine, and child-led exploration worked together to sustain high levels of involvement. This is especially significant in inclusive practice, where varied abilities and preferences can be supported through both structure and freedom.

1.2 Focus and Attention

Physical activity sessions supported the development of focus, rule-following, and self-regulation among children through structured and engaging tasks.

Educators consistently observed that movement-based games improved children's ability to concentrate and follow instructions. E5 explained that "through physical games, children learn to follow instructions and understand rules," while E4 noted that children were "more focused and confident" when activities were clear and structured. These experiences highlight the link between clarity and sustained attention.

Several journal entries confirmed this shift in focus. In a task involving balance cushions and picture matching, a girl demonstrated perseverance, saying "I'll try again" after losing balance, indicating resilient focus and self-regulation. Group games such as Red Light, Green Light helped children practice controlled reactions, while rhythmic activities like hula hoop walking promoted turn-taking and balance. Children used phrases like "It's your turn now" without adult prompting, revealing internalised behavioural regulation.

E5 reported post-activity calm, with children becoming "more focused, less restless, and better able to participate in quieter tasks." Likewise, E1 noticed reduced frustration in some children, suggesting that regular physical play supported emotional balance.

These findings indicate that purposeful movement not only builds physical skills but also reinforces attention, memory, and rule adherence, especially beneficial for children requiring additional support with self-regulation and cognitive control.

1.3 Motivation, Enjoyment, and Initiative

Children displayed high levels of enjoyment, confidence, and self-initiative during physical play, often leading activities, supporting peers, and expressing pride in their accomplishments.

Educators observed that keeping sessions playful and varied boosted children's anticipation and willingness to engage. E1 explained that "we try to keep it fun and varied so that all the children can find something they enjoy," while E5 shared that

the anticipation “added something really special to their week.” E6 highlighted the sensory joy of specific activities, noting that “children absolutely love wet ball activities,” confirming that novelty and variety supported motivation.

Diaries recorded repeated expressions of joy and initiative. Children frequently invented their own games, such as when “one girl said, ‘Let’s pretend we’re walking over jelly,’” to ease peer anxiety. Others led imaginative play, created obstacle courses, or rotated leadership roles without adult direction, showing collaborative autonomy and internal motivation. Phrases like “we did it”, “yay”, and “can I hang it in my room?” captured the emotional value they placed on their efforts.

Several quiet or hesitant children gradually emerged as leaders. One entry noted: “A girl who is usually shy stepped into a leadership role and offered her hand to peers.”

These findings suggest that joyful, flexible, and peer-inclusive environments not only enhanced motivation and enjoyment but also enabled children to explore initiative, empathy, and social leadership through movement-based learning.

1.4 Response to Cues and Social-Emotional Reactions

Children demonstrated increased responsiveness to both verbal and non-verbal cues, alongside noticeable improvements in emotional regulation, confidence, and peer empathy during physical sessions.

Educators consistently reported that children became more attuned to structured verbal instructions and visual modelling. E5 noted that “through physical games, children learn to follow instructions and understand rules,” while E2 observed how cues like “balance now” or “freeze” elicited quick reactions. Children also responded positively to peer prompts, such as “Let’s jump together” or “Turn left!”, suggesting growing sensitivity to shared direction and teamwork.

journal entries reinforced these observations: children frequently mirrored gestures, mimed movements from memory, and gave silent signals like thumbs-up to indicate readiness. Peer imitation and shared rhythm were commonly seen during balancing or song-based tasks. One child clapped silently to cue a peer to go next, highlighting how children internalised social turn-taking norms.

Emotional responses also evolved over time. Initially shy or hesitant children grew more confident, smiling, encouraging others, and initiating cooperative games.

Reactions such as “I’ll try again” or “That’s okay—falling means you’re trying” reflected emotional resilience and safety. Educators noticed calmer moods, improved cooperation, and positive shifts in behaviour after movement sessions, especially among children who initially presented as anxious or withdrawn.

The data clearly indicate that physical play supported not only cognitive attention and cue responsiveness but also nurtured emotional confidence, peer bonding, and inclusion—essential components for social-emotional development in early childhood education.

Theme 2: Physical Activity as a Learning and Regulation Tool

2.1 Improving Motor and Emotional Skills

Physical activity sessions supported the development of both motor coordination and emotional confidence, particularly through varied, playful, and child-led challenges.

Educators observed that structured movement tasks significantly improved children’s control, strength, and spatial awareness. As E1 explained, “physical education supports the development of both fine and gross motor skills—things like jumping, climbing, throwing a ball, or even balancing.” Activities such as balance boards and obstacle courses were described as playful yet purposeful, enhancing coordination, focus, and movement memory. E4 noted that children “learn how their bodies work and how to control movements,” while E6 highlighted the benefits of “small shovels or rakes” for fine motor development.

Journal records confirmed this growth, with repeated circuits improving coordination, balance, and sequencing. Children “tiptoed, jumped, climbed and crawled”, developing integrated motor skills in dynamic environments. Self-directed tasks, such as designing their own obstacle course, supported both motor planning and autonomy.

Emotionally, children demonstrated increased joy, imagination, and pride. Educators reported that physical play helped shy children “open up and start expressing themselves” (E5) and supported “confidence and resilience” (E6). Children expressed

happiness through imaginative movement and celebrated each other's achievements. One journal entry noted: "Peer encouragement and adult praise led to increased smiles, laughter, and pride."

These findings highlight that physical activities not only improve physical competencies but also provide a safe and expressive space for emotional development, empathy, and social connection—particularly beneficial in inclusive early years settings.

2.2 Supporting Self-Regulation and Routine

Regular physical activity contributed to improved emotional regulation and helped establish a predictable routine that supported focus, calmness, and behavioural consistency among children.

Educators repeatedly observed that movement helped children release tension and manage energy in a positive way. E1 noted that "physical play helps children self-regulate and stay focused during other parts of the day," while E4 explained that "when they run, jump, and play, it helps them relax and feel better inside." This emotional reset effect was especially visible after active sessions, with E5 and E2 describing a sense of "afternoon calm" and "emotional balance." E3 emphasised its value as "a good way to use up energy and feel happy."

Diaries confirmed that post-activity periods were marked by calmer moods, greater focus, and more cooperative play. Activities like Freeze Dance and Red Light, Green Light supported impulse control and self-monitoring, while environmental elements such as classical music or vibration plates aided sensory regulation. Children also demonstrated emerging internal control—waiting turns, helping peers, and initiating routines independently.

Movement sessions quickly became part of the children's weekly rhythm. Educators reported that "physical activity is now a key part of how we teach" (E5), with children frequently asking, "Is it activity day today?" Rituals such as thumbs-up check-ins and repeated circuits provided a sense of safety and anticipation. Journal entries noted that children began reusing learned routines during unstructured time, reflecting "ownership of structure."

These findings highlight the role of physical activity in promoting not only emotional balance but also the internalisation of routine, predictability, and self-regulation—key elements in early childhood development and inclusive education.

2.3 Enhancing Classroom Engagement Through Movement

Integrating physical activity into the daily routine enhanced children’s focus, classroom participation, behavioural regulation, and readiness to learn across settings.

Educators consistently observed that physical activity led to calmer, more focused behaviour and smoother classroom transitions. E1 explained, “Physical play helps children self-regulate and stay focused during other parts of the day,” while E5 noted that “children were calmer and more emotionally regulated after physical activities earlier in the day.” E3 added that exercise offered “a good way for them to use up energy and feel happy.”

Journal entries confirmed these insights. Following movement sessions, children demonstrated improved “post-movement concentration,” sustained attention, and smoother transitions into structured learning. One educator noted that “after the game, the children were able to sit more calmly and listen to the instructions,” and another observed that “they were quicker to respond to verbal cues after the obstacle course.”

Increased participation was also noted among children who were usually quiet or preferred solo play. E4 shared, “Even the quieter children spoke up more after playing the team game,” and reflected that “movement isn’t just something fun to fill time; it’s a tool we can use to support learning and development.”

Children anticipated sessions with excitement, often asking, “Is it activity day today?” (E4), reinforcing the value of structured movement as part of their weekly rhythm. The consistent feedback from educators suggests that movement supports learning readiness, enhances behavioural regulation, and fosters social engagement—particularly in inclusive early years classrooms.]

Theme 3 - Educator's Role and Inclusive Practice

3.1 Observing and Reflecting on Development

Educators developed a deeper awareness of children's holistic development through movement, leading to more reflective, responsive, and inclusive practices.

Participation in the programme helped educators observe developmental progress across multiple domains. E1 reflected, "I saw how physical activities contribute not just to motor skills, but also cognitive, emotional, and social development," while E6 noted a personal shift: "I now think more holistically about what movement can do—not just physically but in all areas of development." These insights reshaped their educational lens, with many recognising subtle indicators of growth such as "confidence gained through physical challenges" (E6) and "children who were shy becoming more stable and sure of themselves" (E5).

Daily reflections highlighted real-time developmental changes. E5 observed that "children develop coordination and strength while learning to follow rules," and E3 shared that group play "builds stronger friendships." In Preschool 2, educators documented peer leadership, emergent collaboration, and "internalised learning" where children reused skills like turn-taking and regulation without reminders. One educator commented, "We thought they weren't ready, but it was the environment, not ability."

Practice also evolved. E2 explained, "I reflect weekly on which games worked best and adjust the next session," while E1 noted a shift in planning: "I now plan physical play earlier in the day, when children are more focused." Across the board, educators adapted pacing, layout, and roles in response to children's engagement and sensory needs.

These findings reveal that regular reflection and observation enabled educators to recognise potential, challenge assumptions, and embrace a more inclusive, developmental approach to early years practice.

3.2 Co-Participation and Encouragement

Educators played an active role in modelling inclusive behaviour and encouraging children's participation, creating a positive group dynamic through shared movement, praise, and co-regulation.

Throughout the programme, educators increasingly recognised the importance of their presence and interaction during physical play. E2 explained, "I now try to include teamwork elements like turn-taking and cooperation into our daily activities," while E3 added, "Before the activity, I talk about encouraging each other and having fun, not just winning." E5 confirmed that her planning had shifted to include "specific goals like teamwork, confidence, and coordination."

Co-participation was clearly visible in Preschool 2, where educators consistently joined children in movement games, modelled actions, and celebrated group efforts. One journal entry recorded: "Teachers joined crawling under parachutes and mimicked animal moves with the children," while another noted that "adult participation helped build trust, reduced anxiety, and deepened connection in group tasks."

Encouragement was universal. Educators praised every attempt, as E3 explained: "We celebrate small achievements so that every child feels seen and encouraged." Journal entries highlighted peers cheering each other on with chants like "Jump, jump, you can do it!" and educators reframing mistakes with phrases such as "Falling means you are trying." E4 noted, "Even quieter children engaged more once we changed the structure and added choice," demonstrating the impact of flexibility on inclusion.

These findings reflect how shared adult-child participation and affirming language contributed to an environment of emotional safety, mutual motivation, and equal opportunity for all children to take part—an essential feature of inclusive early years practice.

3.3 Managing Challenges and Supporting Inclusion

While challenges such as limited resources and inconsistent adult participation were noted, educators actively developed adaptive strategies to ensure inclusive and meaningful engagement for all children.

Some educators reported barriers related to planning, space, and equipment. E1 acknowledged, “We sometimes have the tools but not always the ideas – I’d welcome more professional training,” and E6 added, “More resources like cones, balls or balancing tools would make planning easier.” E5 highlighted situational difficulties: “Bad weather can make it tricky, so I look for creative indoor alternatives.” Despite this, many educators embraced a flexible mindset. E2 stated, “In my experience it works well – we’ve made it part of the routine,” while E5 reflected, “Simple activities with minimal equipment showed me I don’t need to overcomplicate things.”

The contrast between Preschool 1 and Preschool 2 revealed the importance of adult presence. In Preschool 1, one journal noted, “I was the only adult leading the activity, which limited opportunities for group reflection,” and that “lack of adult presence meant fewer moments of rich interaction.” In contrast, Preschool 2 educators “helped with setup, joined the play, and encouraged children,” creating “a more emotionally rich environment, especially for quieter or anxious children.”

Adaptations were central to inclusion. E4 explained, “We adjust the same activity to suit quieter children or those with higher energy,” while E3 said, “I guide children who might struggle and pair them with others who can help.” journal entries described task differentiation, pacing for sensory needs, and “peer-assisted inclusion” that allowed hesitant children to participate successfully.

These findings reinforce that thoughtful planning, emotional presence, and simple adjustments can overcome resource constraints and promote meaningful inclusion across ability levels.

Theme 4 - Emotional and Social Inclusion through Movement

4.1 Confidence and Peer Bonding

Movement-based activities promoted growing self-confidence and peer connection, particularly among children who were initially shy or hesitant to participate.

Educators reported visible growth in children's confidence as they engaged in physical challenges. E2 observed, "Children grew in confidence from week to week as they tried new challenges like balancing and jumping," while E5 explained, "Physical activity helps children express themselves and build relationships." E4 noted that "children become more confident movers and find it easier to join games and make friends," illustrating how motor development supported social engagement. Journal entries confirmed this trajectory. One girl completed the obstacle course and proudly exclaimed, "I didn't fall this time!" to which peers responded with claps and smiles, reinforcing a shared sense of pride. Another child who had hesitated at first completed a stepping task, then turned to help a peer—demonstrating "confidence through modelling." Formal moments like the certificate ceremony allowed every child to feel recognised, further reinforcing self-worth and group identity.

Peer relationships also flourished through cooperative play. As E3 shared, "Children who were shy started participating and building friendships." E1 explained, "Through physical play, children learn how to play together, share, and wait their turn," while E2 described the process as "more cooperative and more willing to help each other."

Diaries captured moments of peer encouragement and empathy: "You're doing great!", "Put your head down, like this," and shared laughter under parachutes or while crawling through tunnels. These moments reflect emotional security, mutual respect, and the development of a socially inclusive peer culture built through movement.

4.2 Emotional Safety and Child Voice

Structured physical activity supported emotional safety and fostered a sense of belonging, while child-led choices and creative expression promoted agency and shared ownership of the experience.

Educators highlighted the calming and reassuring effects of movement. E2 noted, "Physical activity helps release tension and anxiety from busy environments," while E5 observed, "Children became more emotionally settled and ready to interact after movement." E4 added that "structured physical activity creates a safe and joyful environment," contributing to consistent emotional regulation. E3 explained, "I set a positive tone and encourage supportiveness so children feel safe to try."

Diaries confirmed that routines such as the thumbs-up ritual offered “a grounding moment for emotional readiness,” and that children responded positively to predictable environments. One quiet girl was invited with, “Come with us – we can help!” while others used comforting language such as “Just pretend they are clouds—step gently.” These examples reflect a peer culture grounded in empathy and emotional reassurance.

Children were also given space to express preferences and contribute to activity design. E1 shared, “When we give them a say, they seem more excited to take part,” and E2 explained, “We observe what they’re drawn to and build from that.” E5 and E4 both described offering choices between movement or story-based games, while E3 reflected, “Before an activity, I ask what they’d enjoy doing today.”

Diaries captured numerous moments of child-led creativity. Children invented rhymes, suggested “robot walks,” renamed stepping pads as “clouds,” and built their own obstacle courses. One girl expressed pride in her work by saying, “Can I hang my certificate at home?” These expressions of voice and identity deepened emotional connection and reinforced a culture of safety, choice, and inclusion.

4.3 Creating a Safe and Inclusive Environment

A predictable, emotionally warm, and physically secure environment enabled children to engage fully, take risks, and support one another, reinforcing inclusion through safety and routine.

Educators placed strong emphasis on structure and clarity to promote a sense of safety. E4 shared, “We explain rules clearly and model safe behaviour before starting,” while E2 noted, “Having a clear structure helped. Children knew what to expect and were more cooperative.” E5 highlighted the physical setting: “The hall space is open, clean, and organised so children can move freely.” For E1, “Children move in a space where they feel safe to try, fall, and try again.” This approach encouraged persistence without fear of failure.

Predictable rituals such as the green thumbs-up helped regulate emotions and prepare children to engage. One journal entry described the ritual as “a shared sense of emotional readiness,” while another noted that “structured circuits gave children something to hold on to emotionally and socially.” Educators often modelled

calmness and joined in play to reduce anxiety, as in the volcano game where a teacher acted as a “fire monster,” turning fear into play.

Children were also given tools for safe interaction with peers. They waited their turn, offered help, and respected personal space. One journal noted “empathic routine” during balance tasks, while another highlighted “positive framing” such as “Falling means you’re trying.”

Shared rituals, playful adult presence, and emotionally attuned routines provided children with an environment where inclusion was not just possible—but natural. The final session, marked by a familiar ritual and shared picnic, offered “symbolic closure” that celebrated both individual and group progress in a secure and inclusive setting.

5. Discussion

5.1 Introduction to the Discussion

This study examined how a physical exercise intervention affects the engagement and responsiveness of preschool children in an inclusive setting. Guided by an interpretivist and critical perspective, the research sought to understand the lived experiences of both children and educators, recognising how relationships, culture, and power dynamics shape participation. Using a participatory action research design, educators acted as co-researchers, contributing actively to the planning, delivery, and reflection processes.

The intervention cycles combined structured physical activities with continuous reflection, enabling ongoing adaptation of sessions to the children's needs, interests, and developmental profiles. The findings indicate that the programme enhanced both behavioural and emotional engagement, with children showing increased focus, willingness to participate, and richer social interactions during group activities. Responsiveness to verbal and non-verbal cues also improved, particularly among children who were initially more reserved or hesitant.

These outcomes reflect the literature showing that inclusive, movement-based approaches can promote motor competence, social connection, and emotional regulation in the early years (Aistear, 2024; Costa et al., 2024; Melillo et al., 2023). At the same time, the results emphasise that educator involvement, adaptability, and a supportive environment are essential for sustaining engagement and responsiveness in diverse groups.

The following sections interpret these findings in relation to the research questions, connect them to the theoretical frameworks discussed in the literature review, and draw out their implications for inclusive early childhood practice.

5.2 Connection to the Research Question

The central research question for this study was:

How does a physical exercise intervention affect the engagement and responsiveness of preschool children in an inclusive setting?

The findings provide clear evidence that the intervention positively influenced both engagement and responsiveness, confirming the value of integrating structured, inclusive movement into early childhood education.

Engagement was reflected in high levels of active participation, growing anticipation for activity days, and the emergence of self-initiated play and leadership roles. Even children who were initially hesitant became more confident and willing to join in, often leading or adapting activities. This progression aligns with the literature highlighting that predictable, playful, and child-led experiences foster sustained motivation and inclusion (Costa et al., 2024; Aistear, 2024).

Responsiveness improved in both verbal and non-verbal domains. Children followed instructions more consistently, reacted more quickly to cues, and engaged in peer-led prompting. Visual modelling, structured repetition, and collaborative games enhanced their ability to interpret and respond appropriately to guidance. These outcomes support earlier findings that physical activity, especially when scaffolded by educators, strengthens attention, self-regulation, and social communication (Melillo et al., 2023; Haugland et al., 2024).

The results also show that the inclusive design of the intervention—combining structure with flexibility—was crucial. Activities could be adapted to accommodate varied abilities, ensuring that all children experienced success. Educator co-participation, reflective planning, and affirming feedback reinforced emotional safety, enabling children to take risks, persist through challenges, and form positive peer relationships.

In summary, the study demonstrates that a thoughtfully designed physical activity intervention can significantly enhance both engagement and responsiveness in inclusive preschool contexts, validating the relevance of movement-based learning as a tool for fostering participation, emotional confidence, and social connection.

5.3 Child Engagement and Responsiveness

The findings from Theme 1 indicate that the physical exercise intervention meaningfully enhanced children's engagement and responsiveness, supporting the core argument from the literature review that movement-rich, inclusive environments

promote participation, agency, and socio-emotional development in the early years (Aistear, 2024; Costa et al., 2024).

Active participation was evident throughout the programme, with children anticipating activity days, engaging enthusiastically, and in some cases initiating their own games and obstacle courses. This reflects Aistear's (2024) emphasis on embedding movement into daily routines to foster children's agency, exploration, and wellbeing. The progression from initial hesitation to full involvement mirrors Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978), where participation in supported, social contexts enables learners to operate within and eventually expand their Zone of Proximal Development. It also echoes the Super Quinas findings (Costa et al., 2024), where structured but adaptable sessions increased attendance, enthusiasm, and willingness to participate in group play.

Focus and attention improved notably during and after physical sessions, with children following rules, persisting in challenges, and regulating emotions. This outcome supports evidence linking physical activity to the strengthening of executive functions—such as inhibitory control and working memory—particularly in the preschool years (Diamond, 2000; Haugland et al., 2024). Structured games like Red Light, Green Light and balancing activities provided natural contexts for practising these skills, aligning with Lum et al. (2022), who found that consistent, educator-led motor activities improved attentional control and task persistence in young children.

The increase in motivation, enjoyment, and initiative further supports literature connecting play-based, inclusive pedagogy to social learning and peer collaboration. According to Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977), children model behaviours observed in peers and trusted adults; in this study, the visible leadership of some children encouraged others to take on new roles, reflecting the cooperative, peer-supported learning described by Wasenius et al. (2023). The children's imaginative adaptations, such as inventing "jelly walks" to reduce peer anxiety, also mirror the inclusive, creative problem-solving encouraged by Universal Design for Learning (PDST, 2021) and Florian & Black-Hawkins's (2011) principle of using diversity as a resource for learning.

Responsiveness to verbal and non-verbal cues through mirroring gestures, responding to peer prompts, and using turn-taking signals demonstrates the social communication benefits identified in the literature. Peer-to-peer direction aligns with

the cooperative interaction benefits described by Roth & Kriemler (2015), where group-based physical activities promoted teamwork, empathy, and mutual regulation. Improvements in emotional resilience, such as the willingness to “try again” after mistakes, reflect findings from Mak, Chan & Capio (2021) that link motor competence to self-confidence and persistence, particularly in inclusive settings where success is experienced alongside peers.

In conclusion, Theme 1 validates the literature’s position that embedding adaptable, enjoyable, and collaborative physical activity into early years practice not only develops motor and cognitive skills but also builds engagement, self-regulation, empathy, and emotional confidence. These gains are most effectively realised when the intervention is rooted in inclusive pedagogy, allows for child-led contributions, and is consistently supported by educator modelling principles consistently highlighted across Aistear (2024), PDST (2021), and recent international evidence.

5.4 Physical Activity as a Learning and Regulation Tool

The findings under Theme 2 highlight the dual role of physical activity (PA) in supporting both developmental learning and emotional regulation. This aligns with the literature reviewed, which consistently positions movement as central to holistic early childhood development (World Health Organization, 2010; Diamond, 2000; Aistear, 2024).

5.4.1 Improving motor and emotional skills

The observed gains in coordination, balance, spatial awareness, and fine motor control reflect the evidence that early gross and fine motor competence is a predictor of later physical activity participation, self-esteem, and academic outcomes (Barnett et al., 2008; Grissmer et al., 2010). Structured yet playful tasks, such as balance boards and obstacle courses, match the motor skill development strategies described in the Move Well, Move Often resource (PDST, 2021) and the Demonstration Project on In-School and Early Years Therapy Support (2020), both of which promote purposeful activities tailored to developmental stages.

The emotional gains reported greater confidence, willingness to self-express, and pride in achievements which are consistent with research by Mak, Chan & Capio

(2021), which links motor competence to resilience and emotional wellbeing, particularly in inclusive contexts. The self-directed challenges described here also echo Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978) and Piaget's (1962) emphasis on autonomy and experiential learning, as children learned through active exploration and social interaction.

5.4.2 Supporting self-regulation and routine

Educators' observations of calmer moods, greater focus, and behavioural consistency after PA sessions align with findings by Haugland et al. (2024) and Lum et al. (2022) that movement can improve executive functions and emotional regulation in early years settings. Games like Freeze Dance and Red Light, Green Light provided embedded opportunities to practise impulse control, directly supporting Aistear's (2024) Wellbeing theme, which emphasises structured, playful routines for emotional stability.

The establishment of predictable rituals such as the thumbs-up check-ins not only reduced anxiety but also supported the internalisation of behavioural expectations. This is in line with the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principle of multiple means of engagement (PDST, 2021), ensuring that routines are accessible and meaningful for all learners, including those with additional needs.

5.4.3 Enhancing classroom engagement through movement

Post-activity improvements in concentration, smoother transitions, and increased participation by quieter children reinforce the literature that positions PA as a catalyst for learning readiness (Pate et al., 2016; Costa et al., 2024). Educators' feedback mirrors Oliver et al. (2007) and Stuart (2021), who note that physical activity can be a practical tool for managing classroom energy levels and sustaining engagement in subsequent academic tasks.

The evidence that PA served as both a regulation mechanism and a learning enabler also reflects Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977), with children modelling on-task behaviours observed in peers during and after active play. This combination of immediate regulatory effects and longer-term learning benefits underscores the role of PA as an essential, not optional, component of inclusive early childhood pedagogy.

In summary, Theme 2 confirms that structured, inclusive physical activity can simultaneously build physical competence, support emotional resilience, and improve behavioural regulation, directly enhancing learning conditions in preschool settings. These outcomes validate calls in the literature (Aistear, 2024; PDST, 2021; Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011) to integrate PA as a core pedagogical tool, embedded in daily routines and responsive to the diverse needs of all children.

5.5 Educator's Role and Inclusive Practice

The findings from Theme 3 highlight the central role of educators in embedding inclusive, movement-based learning into early childhood practice. This is strongly supported by the literature, which consistently identifies educator engagement, reflection, and adaptability as key drivers of successful physical activity interventions (Duff, 2018; Buckler & Bredin, 2021; O'Byrne, Dinneen & Coppinger, 2023).

5.5.1 Observing and reflecting on development

Educators in this study developed a deeper understanding of children's holistic development through active observation and reflection. This aligns with Schön's (1983) Reflective Practitioner model, which emphasises continuous reflection during and after practice to improve responsiveness and inclusion. The recognition that movement contributes not only to motor skills but also to cognitive, emotional, and social growth mirrors the integrated developmental perspective of Aistear (2024) and the Dynamic Systems Theory (Thelen, 1989), which view learning as the result of complex interactions between the child, environment, and experiences.

The shift from focusing solely on physical skills to adopting a holistic developmental lens parallels the findings of the Demonstration Project on In-School and Early Years Therapy Support (2020), where structured physical activities became opportunities for observing and supporting wider developmental competencies, including confidence and social interaction.

5.5.2 Co-participation and encouragement

The positive impact of educator co-participation in this study strongly echoes Bandura's (1977) Social Learning Theory, which holds that children learn behaviours,

attitudes, and skills by observing and imitating role models. When educators modelled teamwork, celebrated effort, and reframed mistakes as learning opportunities, children mirrored these behaviours, fostering an emotionally safe and motivating environment.

This is consistent with Wasenius et al. (2023), who found that adaptable movement-based activities led by engaged educators promoted inclusion by creating opportunities for all children to experience success. It also reflects Florian & Black-Hawkins's (2011) principle of using diversity as a resource, as adult modelling and inclusive encouragement supported peer empathy and participation across ability levels.

5.5.3 Managing challenges and supporting inclusion

The challenges noted such as limited resources and inconsistent adult participation are well-documented in the literature (Oliver et al., 2007; Hesketh et al., 2017). However, the flexible and creative solutions adopted by educators in this study mirror recommendations from the Universal Design for Learning framework (PDST, 2021), which advocates for adaptability, multiple means of engagement, and accessible activity design to remove participation barriers.

The contrast between Preschool 1 and Preschool 2 underscores the evidence from O'Byrne, Dinneen & Coppinger (2023) that educator presence and engagement are decisive factors in achieving and sustaining inclusive practice. In settings where educators actively joined in, provided encouragement, and adapted activities, children, particularly those who were quieter or more hesitant, demonstrated greater emotional engagement and participation.

In summary, Theme 3 reinforces the literature's position that educator involvement is not an optional enhancement but a core element of inclusive physical activity interventions. Through reflective observation, co-participation, and adaptive planning, educators can transform movement sessions into rich opportunities for learning, regulation, and social connection, fulfilling the inclusive aims outlined in Aistear (2024), Síolta (Department of Education and Skills, 2017), and contemporary inclusive pedagogy.

5.6 Emotional and Social Inclusion through Movement

The findings from Theme 4 highlight how structured, inclusive physical activity sessions can strengthen confidence, peer relationships, emotional safety, and a sense of belonging in early childhood settings. These outcomes strongly align with the literature emphasising that movement-based learning environments foster both social and emotional development when designed to be inclusive, predictable, and child-centred (Aistear, 2024; Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011; Wasenius et al., 2018).

5.6.1 Confidence and peer bonding

The observed increases in self-confidence, particularly among initially hesitant or shy children, reflect the research of Mak, Chan & Capio (2021), which links motor competence to higher self-esteem and social participation. Educators' accounts of children taking on new challenges and celebrating success with peers illustrate Bandura's (1977) Social Learning Theory, where confidence is built through modelling, feedback, and shared achievement. The role of cooperative games in strengthening friendships and empathy mirrors findings by Roth & Kriemler (2015), who identified that group-based physical activities enhance peer relationships and promote inclusion for children of diverse abilities.

5.6.2 Emotional safety and child voice

The predictable structure, positive reinforcement, and safe environment described in the findings are consistent with Aistear's (2024) Wellbeing theme, which highlights emotional security as a prerequisite for engagement and learning. The literature also stresses that inclusive practice is strengthened when children have agency in shaping activities (PDST, 2021; Universal Design for Learning framework). The examples of children renaming equipment, inventing movements, and choosing between activity options align with Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978), which positions choice, creativity, and collaborative meaning-making as drivers of deeper engagement.

5.6.3 Creating a safe and inclusive environment

The emphasis educators placed on clear rules, modelling safe behaviour, and maintaining an organised, accessible space reflects best practice guidance from Síolta (Department of Education and Skills, 2017) and the TREE model (PDST, 2021), which advocate for removing physical and emotional barriers to participation. Predictable rituals such as the green thumbs-up acted as emotional anchors, similar to the structured routines recommended in sensory regulation literature (Ayres, 2002; Pajk Kraljević & Podhraski, 2023) to support children's readiness for engagement.

The findings also illustrate how adult participation and positive framing such as "Falling means you're trying" reduce performance anxiety and reframe risk-taking as part of learning. This approach resonates with the inclusive pedagogy principles described by Florian & Black-Hawkins (2011), which value every child's contribution and promote resilience by normalising challenge and error as part of the learning process.

In summary, Theme 4 reinforces that inclusive physical activity sessions can be powerful tools for building emotional confidence, strengthening peer connections, and creating a secure environment where all children can participate fully. These outcomes validate the literature's call (Aistear, 2024; PDST, 2021; Wasenius et al., 2018) to integrate movement as both a developmental and social inclusion strategy, ensuring that emotional safety and child voice are central to early years practice.

5.7 Comparison with Existing Literature

The findings of this study align closely with both the theoretical foundations and the empirical evidence outlined in the literature review, reinforcing the position that inclusive, movement-based approaches are highly effective in promoting engagement, responsiveness, and holistic development in early childhood education.

5.7.1 Active participation and motivation

The observed increase in active participation and anticipation for activity days reflects earlier research indicating that predictable routines, combined with novelty and child choice, enhance intrinsic motivation to engage (Costa et al., 2024; Aistear, 2024).

The success of this study's approach mirrors the outcomes of the Super Quinas

programme, where regular, well-structured sessions fostered excitement, sustained involvement, and a sense of ownership over learning experiences. This aligns with Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985), which emphasises that autonomy, competence, and relatedness are key drivers of motivation elements clearly present in the intervention through child-led adaptations, skill progression, and peer collaboration.

5.7.2 Focus, self-regulation, and responsiveness

The documented improvements in focus, self-regulation, and responsiveness to both verbal and non-verbal cues correspond with studies highlighting the role of physical activity in strengthening executive functions, including attention control, working memory, and behavioural regulation (Diamond, 2000; Haugland et al., 2024). Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978) provides a relevant lens here: educator modelling, scaffolding, and peer interaction helped children move from assisted to independent mastery, reflecting the progression within the Zone of Proximal Development.

5.7.3 Social learning and cooperative behaviours

The findings also resonate with Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977), which posits that behaviours are acquired through observation, imitation, and modelling. Peer-led prompts, shared tasks, and collaborative play in this study encouraged the imitation of positive behaviours, consistent with evidence that cooperative physical activities promote empathy, prosocial behaviour, and inclusive peer cultures (Wasenius et al., 2018; Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011). This interplay of modelling and peer reinforcement reflects Situated Learning Theory (Lave & Wenger, 1991), where participation in shared, meaningful activities fosters community and mutual engagement.

5.7.4 Motor skill development and emotional benefits

Motor skill improvements observed in children such as enhanced balance, coordination, and strength support a substantial body of literature showing that structured movement in early years can produce measurable gains in both gross and fine motor competence (Barnett et al., 2008; Strooband et al., 2020). Importantly,

these physical gains were linked to emotional benefits, such as increased confidence and resilience, supporting Mak, Chan & Capio's (2021) assertion that motor competence underpins self-esteem and willingness to participate in new challenges. The Dynamic Systems Theory (Thelen, 1989) further explains these findings, framing motor development as the result of continuous interaction between biological, environmental, and experiential factors a dynamic well captured in this study's adaptable, child-centred activities.

5.7.5 Educator co-participation and reflective practice

The emphasis on educator co-participation and reflective practice echoes Duff's (2018) findings that sustained, embedded professional development is essential for inclusive approaches to thrive. The contrast between settings with high and low adult participation reinforces O'Byrne, Dinneen & Coppinger's (2023) conclusion that educator engagement is a determining factor in the success of physical activity programmes. Schön's (1983) Reflective Practitioner model is particularly relevant: educators in this study engaged in ongoing reflection, adjusted activities responsively, and integrated physical activity into broader pedagogical goals hallmarks of reflective, adaptive practice.

5.7.6 Extending current knowledge

Overall, the results of this study both support and extend the existing body of knowledge by demonstrating how a Participatory Action Research approach, grounded in inclusive pedagogy, can operationalise theoretical principles into practical, sustainable benefits for diverse preschool populations. The combination of child agency, educator engagement, and adaptable, theory-informed activities offers a replicable model for integrating physical activity as a vehicle for both learning and inclusion, in line with national frameworks such as Aistear (2024) and Síolta (Department of Education and Skills, 2017).

5.8 Explaining Unexpected or Divergent Findings

While the overall findings of this study align strongly with the literature on inclusive physical activity interventions, several observations diverged from expectations or revealed nuances underexplored in previous research.

5.8.1 Variation in engagement between settings

One unexpected element was the marked difference in engagement between Preschool 1 and Preschool 2 despite the identical intervention design. In Preschool 2, where educators consistently co-participated, modelled behaviours, and provided encouragement, children's confidence and peer collaboration developed more rapidly. In contrast, Preschool 1 where adult participation was less frequent saw slower gains, particularly among quieter or more hesitant children. This variation underscores evidence from O'Byrne, Dinneen & Coppinger (2023) and Duff (2018) that educator involvement is a determining factor in the success of physical activity interventions. It also reinforces Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977), which posits that observational learning relies on consistent, credible role models. The difference here suggests that modelling and co-participation are not supplementary elements but essential mechanisms for fostering engagement, especially in inclusive environments.

5.8.2 Rapid improvement in cue responsiveness

Another divergence from expected trends was the speed with which initially hesitant children improved their responsiveness to verbal and non-verbal cues. Literature such as Haugland et al. (2024) often describes this progression as gradual, particularly for children with lower baseline social confidence. In this study, predictable routines, the strategic use of visual and verbal cues, and peer modelling seemed to accelerate this process. From a Vygotskian perspective, the combination of scaffolding, repetition, and social interaction within the Zone of Proximal Development may have reduced cognitive load and anxiety, enabling faster acquisition of responsive behaviours. The structured yet flexible nature of activities aligns with the Universal Design for Learning (PDST, 2021), which advocates for multiple means of engagement to meet diverse learner needs.

5.8.3 High levels of self-initiated leadership and creativity

The extent of peer-initiated leadership, problem-solving, and creative adaptation exceeded what is commonly reported in the literature. While the role of child-led play in enhancing engagement is well established (Vygotsky, 1978; Aistear, 2024), the findings here suggest that when children experience psychological safety and see

their input visibly valued, they may surpass anticipated levels of agency. This resonates with Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985), which emphasises that autonomy and relatedness foster intrinsic motivation and creative risk-taking. The invention of new games, re-purposing of materials, and collaborative rule modifications demonstrate the social-constructivist principle that learning is most powerful when children co-create meaning and activities.

5.8.4 Limited transfer to unstructured physical activity

Finally, the study did not record a significant increase in unstructured daily physical activity outside the planned sessions. This mirrors mixed findings from programmes such as Mighty Moves (Bellows & Anderson, 2013), where gains in structured settings did not automatically translate into increased habitual activity. From an ecological systems perspective (Bronfenbrenner, 1979), this limitation may stem from broader environmental influences such as home routines, outdoor space availability, or community opportunities that were beyond the scope of the intervention. It highlights the persistent challenge of embedding physical activity behaviours across microsystems, suggesting the need for greater family and community integration in future programme design.

5.8.5 Summary

These divergences indicate that while inclusive physical activity interventions can reliably enhance engagement, responsiveness, and social cohesion within the structured programme, their broader and sustained impact depends heavily on the interplay of educator participation, environmental consistency, and opportunities for skill and behaviour transfer into unstructured and home settings.

5.9 Practical Implications

The results of this study offer several theoretically grounded and practice-oriented insights for enhancing engagement and responsiveness through physical activity (PA) interventions in inclusive preschool settings.

5.9.1 Educator co-participation as a driver of success

The findings confirm that active educator participation through modelling, shared movement, and consistent encouragement is a critical determinant of success. This mirrors Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977), which posits that children learn behaviours, attitudes, and skills through observing credible role models. When educators positioned themselves as co-learners rather than peripheral facilitators, children displayed greater focus, confidence, and peer cooperation. This suggests that early years training programmes should integrate practical modules on leading and participating in PA, reinforcing educators' identities as active pedagogical partners.

5.9.2 Structured routines with flexible adaptation

The intervention demonstrated the value of predictable routines paired with adaptive flexibility. Structured formats such as warm-up games, skill-based challenges, and closing rituals provided a secure framework that reduced anxiety and supported self-regulation (Aistear, 2024; PDST, 2021). Simultaneously, opportunities for choice and creative input supported children's autonomy and intrinsic motivation, consistent with Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985). Practitioners should adopt a "core-plus-flex" model: embedding consistent elements to provide stability, while incorporating child-led modifications to maintain engagement and agency.

5.9.3 Physical activity as a tool for self-regulation

Games like Red Light, Green Light, balance challenges, and cooperative obstacle courses not only enhanced motor competence but also supported smoother transitions into calmer, more focused learning. This aligns with Diamond's (2000) research on the role of PA in developing executive functions such as inhibitory control and attentional focus. Strategic placement of movement sessions before cognitively demanding tasks can support behavioural regulation and optimise learning readiness.

5.9.4 Inclusive design through Universal Design for Learning (UDL)

Peer-assisted participation, differentiated task difficulty, and varied cueing methods used in this study exemplify the application of UDL principles (PDST, 2021). By providing multiple means of engagement, representation, and action, educators ensured equitable access for children with varied abilities, sensory profiles, and confidence levels. This approach is particularly important in inclusive classrooms, where barriers to participation may differ widely between individuals.

5.9.5 Reflective practice and collaborative problem-solving

Regular reflection meetings among educators allowed for the exchange of observations, identification of emerging challenges, and collaborative adjustments to activity design. This practice reflects Schön's (1983) Reflective Practitioner model and supports continuous improvement in inclusive pedagogy. Embedding such cycles into early years practice can help staff respond dynamically to environmental constraints such as limited space or resources while maintaining high-quality, inclusive PA experiences.

5.9.6 Summary

In conclusion, the findings position inclusive PA interventions not as supplemental extras but as essential, curriculum-integrated tools for promoting holistic development, building community, and fostering equity in participation. When grounded in theory, supported by skilled and engaged educators, and embedded within reflective, adaptable practice, PA becomes a powerful mechanism for ensuring that every child has the opportunity to participate, succeed, and thrive.

5.10 Limitations

While this study provides valuable insights into the impact of a physical exercise intervention on engagement and responsiveness in inclusive preschool settings, several limitations must be acknowledged to contextualise the findings and guide future research design.

5.10.1 Single-site scope

The scope of the study was limited to one preschool with two classroom groups. Although the groups differed in educator participation, the single-site context reduces the generalisability of findings. As Creswell & Plano Clark (2017) note, site-specific cultural, structural, and resourcing factors can influence intervention outcomes. Variations in institutional ethos, staff training, and available facilities across other early years settings may produce different results, limiting the external validity of this study.

5.10.2 Small sample size

The relatively small sample, approximately 30–35 children and six educators, enabled in-depth qualitative observation but limits statistical robustness. While qualitative research often prioritises depth over breadth (Patton, 2015), the modest sample restricts the ability to make broad generalisations or detect subtler trends across sub-groups of children.

5.10.3 Dual role of the researcher

The researcher's dual role as both programme facilitator and data collector may have introduced bias. This is a common concern in action research (McNiff & Whitehead, 2011), where researcher presence can shape participant behaviour. Strategies such as reflexive journaling, triangulation of observational and interview data, and regular supervisory feedback were applied to minimise bias, but the potential influence of the researcher's expectations cannot be entirely ruled out.

5.10.4 Short intervention duration

The relatively short duration of the intervention limited the ability to assess long-term sustainability of outcomes. Without longitudinal follow-up, it is unclear whether improvements in engagement, responsiveness, and self-regulation would persist over time or transfer to other contexts, an issue noted in previous evaluations of early years physical activity programmes (e.g., Bellows & Anderson, 2013).

5.10. 5 Indirect child voice

Data from children's perspectives were collected indirectly via educator reflections and researcher observation, rather than through direct child interviews or participatory feedback tools. While this approach was developmentally appropriate for the age group, it risks filtering experiences through adult interpretation, potentially missing nuances in children's subjective perceptions (Clark, 2017).

5.10.11 External influencing factors

External variables such as weather conditions limiting outdoor activity, variations in daily classroom routines, and individual child circumstances may have influenced engagement and responsiveness. From an ecological systems perspective (Bronfenbrenner, 1979), these mesosystem and exosystem factors interact dynamically with intervention effects, making it difficult to isolate outcomes solely attributable to the programme.

5.10.12 Summary

Recognising these limitations is essential for interpreting the findings within their proper context. They highlight the need for multi-site replication, larger and more diverse samples, strategies to capture authentic child voice, and longitudinal follow-up to examine the durability and transferability of gains.

5.11 Recommendations for Future Research

Building on the findings and methodological limitations of this study, several recommendations can guide future research into inclusive physical activity (PA) interventions in early childhood education (ECE) settings.

5.11.1 Expand sample size and contextual diversity

Future studies should extend beyond a single site to include multiple preschools with varied socio-economic contexts, physical environments, and staff experience levels. Multi-site designs would enhance the external validity of findings (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017) and enable cross-case comparisons between different models of inclusive pedagogy. This would also allow for exploration of how contextual variables

such as facility design, staff-child ratios, and cultural attitudes toward physical activity affect intervention outcomes.

5.11.2 Adopt longitudinal research designs

The sustainability of gains in engagement, responsiveness, and self-regulation remains unclear. Longitudinal designs following children over several months or ideally into later school years would clarify whether benefits persist and whether they generalise to other learning domains. This aligns with calls in early years research (Bellows & Anderson, 2013) for greater understanding of the maintenance effect of PA interventions.

5.11.3 Incorporate authentic child voice

Although this study captured children's perspectives indirectly, future research should use developmentally appropriate participatory methods such as photo-elicitation, drawing activities, "talking mats," or simple choice-based feedback to gain a richer understanding of children's lived experiences (Clark, 2017). This would align with Lundy's Model of Participation (2007), ensuring that children have space, voice, audience, and influence in shaping PA provision.

5.11.4 Examine the role of educator professional development

Given that educator co-participation emerged as a key driver of success, future studies could compare interventions with and without targeted professional development on inclusive PA delivery. This would help quantify the impact of capacity-building and align with the Reflective Practitioner approach (Schön, 1983), which positions continuous learning as central to effective practice.

5.11.5 Investigate integration with other developmental domains

Further research should explore how PA can be purposefully linked to domains such as language, literacy, or numeracy without diluting developmental or academic outcomes. This supports the holistic learning principle in Aistear (2024) and could demonstrate how PA enhances rather than competes with curriculum priorities.

5.11.6 Identify barriers and facilitators to sustained activity beyond sessions

Finally, the challenge of transferring PA behaviours beyond structured sessions warrants deeper investigation. Using an ecological systems theory lens (Bronfenbrenner, 1979), future work could examine how family engagement, access to safe outdoor spaces, and community partnerships influence the continuity of active behaviours in home and community contexts.

5.11.7 Summary

By addressing these areas, future research can strengthen the evidence base, inform early years policy, and provide practitioners with scalable, sustainable strategies to embed inclusive PA into the daily fabric of early childhood education.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

This dissertation studied how a physical activity intervention can support engagement and responsiveness in preschool children in inclusive classrooms. The research was based on an interpretivist and critical approach, using participatory action research to include both teachers and children in the process. The study showed that physical activity is not only useful for improving children's motor skills but also helps them to focus, to respond better to instructions, and to build confidence and positive relationships with their peers.

One of the main findings is that physical activity can be a strong tool for inclusion. Children were more motivated, they looked forward to the activity days, and many of them began to take initiative and lead their peers. They also became more responsive to verbal and non-verbal cues, which supported cooperation and teamwork. At the same time, physical play gave children space to express emotions, to calm down, and to feel safe in the group. This shows that physical activity should be understood as an important part of early education and not as something extra.

The role of educators was also very important. When teachers joined the activities, gave encouragement, and reflected on the children's needs, the results were much stronger. In situations where educators were less involved, the impact on children was weaker. This confirms that professional development and reflective practice are central for making physical activity inclusive and meaningful.

There are some limits to this study. It was carried out in only one preschool with a small number of participants, so the results cannot represent every context. The short time frame means it was not possible to see if the positive effects would last over a longer period. Also, most of the children's views were gathered indirectly through adult observation, which shows the need for more direct ways of including children's voices in future studies.

Even with these limits, the study has important implications. It shows that physical activity can be used as a practical and effective method to improve engagement and responsiveness in inclusive preschool settings. It suggests that educators should include physical activity in everyday routines and that policies such as Aistear and Síolta can be supported with more training and resources for teachers.

In this study, children's voices were included in a simple way. Each day they were asked if they wanted to take part in the activity, and they could answer with a thumbs-up using a visual cue. This showed their choice and agency, but future research could develop even more ways to capture children's perspectives.

In conclusion, this dissertation has shown that physical activity is more than movement or exercise. It is a way of learning, connecting, and belonging. When teachers are active partners and when activities are flexible and inclusive, children develop not only physical skills but also confidence, social relationships, and the ability to respond to the world around them. An important point is that children's voices were included in a simple way during the study. Each day they were asked if they wanted to take part in the activity, and they answered with a thumbs-up using a visual cue. This gave them choice and agency, while also reminding us that future research should create even more direct ways to capture children's perspectives. Physical activity is therefore an essential part of early childhood education and a pathway to inclusion.

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Apeendices

Appendix A

Dear Parent/Guardian,

My name is **Kristina Rautek Potocnik**, and I am currently in my final semester of the **Master of Arts in Early Intervention and Inclusive Practice for Children** at the **Faculty of Business & Humanities, Department of Sport & Early Childhood, Technological University of the Shannon (TUS)**.

As part of my final semester requirements, I am conducting a research project titled **“Inclusive Physical Education in the Preschool Curriculum: A Study on Its Impact on Children's Development and Educators' Perspectives.”**

I would greatly appreciate your **consent for your child's participation** in this research. The study will involve a **play-based physical exercise program** designed to support **children's development and engagement in inclusive settings**. The program includes structured physical activities for preschool-aged children, lasting 15 to 40 minutes depending on the setting (classroom, playground, or hall). Activities are developmentally appropriate, engaging, and inclusive.

This movement-based intervention aims to improve motor skills, coordination, balance, and overall well-being while encouraging social interaction and cognitive engagement. Activities include: guided play and sensory-motor exercises, music and movement, action-based storytelling, nature exploration, cooperative movement games, etc.

Children will take part in interactive exercises like parachute games, rhythm-based movements, obstacle courses, and imaginative role-play. The goal is to create an enjoyable and inclusive environment where all children can develop movement skills and benefit from social and cognitive engagement.

Observations will be conducted **during regular preschool activities**, and the insights gathered will contribute to understanding how such programs **impact children's development, learning, and social interactions**.

Participation in this study is **entirely voluntary**, and you may **withdraw your consent at any time** without any consequences. All information collected will remain **strictly confidential** and will be used **solely for the purposes of this research**. Identification codes will be assigned instead of personal data to **ensure your child's privacy**, and no identifiable information will appear in the research findings.

Excerpts from the study may be **included in my final dissertation** and may also be used in **future academic presentations and publications** to advance research in the field of **inclusive physical education**. All data will be **securely stored in accordance with TUS data management policies** and will be permanently **deleted seven years after the study is completed**, as per the **TUS Research Ethics Policy** (Technological University of the Shannon, 2023, p. 23).

If you agree to your child's participation, please review and sign the attached **Parental Consent Form**.

Should you have any **questions or require further information**, please feel free to contact me at kristinapotocnik0@gmail.com or **089 450 7600**. If you require further clarification or have any **ethical concerns**, you may also contact my **research supervisor, Helen Maher**, at helen.maher@tus.ie.

Thank you for your time and consideration in supporting this research. Your participation will play a valuable role in **advancing our understanding of inclusive physical education in preschool settings**.

Yours sincerely,
Kristina Rautek Potocnik

Date: ___ / ___ / ___

Parental Guardian Consent Form

Research Title:

Inclusive Physical Education in the Preschool Curriculum: A Study on Its Impact on Children's Development and Educators' Perspectives

I, _____, agree to allow my child, _____, to participate in the above research project.

The nature of my child's participation has been fully explained to me, and I understand how the information collected will be used.

- I understand that my child will take part in **regular preschool activities** as part of a **play-based physical exercise intervention**. Observations of my child's participation will be **documented for research purposes**.
- My child's participation is **entirely voluntary**.
- I am entitled to **full confidentiality** regarding my child's participation, as well as the **secure storage and use** of their personal details.
- I understand that I have the **right to withdraw my consent at any time**, and my child's participation in the study can end **without any negative consequences**.
- If I withdraw my child from the study, all related data will be **removed and permanently destroyed**.
- I am permitted to view any **research and transcripts** related to my child's participation and can request a **copy of the final research report** from the researcher.
- All information will remain **strictly confidential** and will be used **solely for the purposes of this research study**.
- I understand that **identification codes** will be used to **protect my child's anonymity and confidentiality**, and any **identifying details, such as names of people or places, will be changed**.
- I agree that **anonymized quotations or data** may be included in the research findings and may be used for **academic presentations or publications**.
- I understand that all research data will be **securely stored in compliance with TUS data management policies** and will be **destroyed seven years after the study is completed** (Technological University of the Shannon, 2023, p. 23).

Pseudonym Preference:

I would like the pseudonym used for any references to my child to be:

_____.

Yours sincerely,

Signature of Parent/Guardian

Date: ___ / ___ / ___

Appendix B

Dear Participant,

My name is **Kristina Rautek Potocnik**, and I am currently in my final semester of the **Master of Arts in Early Intervention and Inclusive Practice for Children** at the **Faculty of Business & Humanities, Department of Sport & Early Childhood, Technological University of the Shannon (TUS)**. As part of my final semester requirements, I am conducting a research project titled **“Inclusive Physical Education in the Preschool Curriculum: A Study on Its Impact on Children's Development and Educators' Perspectives.”**

I would greatly appreciate your participation in this research by taking part in an **interview**. The interview is designed to explore your **perspectives on implementing physical exercise activities in inclusive preschool settings**, as well as your experiences regarding **children's engagement and responsiveness**. The interview will be **semi-structured**, allowing for open discussion while covering key themes relevant to this research. It will take approximately **20 minutes** and can be conducted at a **time and place that is most convenient for you**.

Participation in this study is **entirely voluntary**, and you may **withdraw at any time** without any consequences. With your permission, the interview will be **audio recorded** to ensure accuracy in data collection. All responses will remain **strictly confidential** and will be used **solely for the purposes of this research**. Identification codes will be assigned to anonymize your responses, and no personally identifiable data will be linked to your contributions. The recordings and transcripts will be **securely stored**, and all data will be **destroyed seven years after the study is completed**, in accordance with **TUS Research Ethics Policy**.

If you would like to participate in this study, I will provide an **information sheet** detailing the study's purpose, as well as a **consent form** for you to sign before the interview.

If you have any **questions, concerns, or complaints** about this research, please feel free to contact me at kristinapotocnik0@gmail.com or **089 450 7600**. You may also contact my **research supervisor, Helen Maher**, at helen.maher@tus.ie if you require further clarification or have any ethical concerns regarding the study.

Thank you for your time and valuable contribution, which will play a significant role in advancing research in this area.

Yours sincerely,

Kristina Rautek Potocnik

Date: ___ / ___ / ___

Research Participant Consent Form

Research Title:

Inclusive Physical Education in the Preschool Curriculum: A Study on Its Impact on Children's Development and Educators' Perspectives

I, _____, agree to take part in the above research project.

The nature of my participation has been fully explained to me, and I understand how the information collected will be used.

- I understand that I will take part in a **semi-structured interview lasting approximately 20 minutes**.
- My participation is **completely voluntary**.
- I am entitled to **full confidentiality** regarding my participation, as well as the **secure storage and use** of my personal details.
- I understand that I have the **right to withdraw** from this study at any time, without providing a reason.
- If I withdraw from the study, there will be **no negative consequences**.
- I am permitted to view all **research data and transcripts** related to my participation and can request a copy of the **final research report** from the researcher.
- All information will remain **strictly confidential** and will be used **solely for the purposes of this research study**.
- I understand that **identification codes will be used** to protect my anonymity and confidentiality, and any **identifying details, such as names of people or places, will be changed**.
- I agree that **anonymized quotations** from my responses may be used in the research.

Pseudonym Preference:

I would like the pseudonym used for direct quotations from me to be:

_____.

Participant's Signature: _____

Date: ___ / ___ / ___

Researcher's Signature: _____

Date: ___ / ___ / ___

Let's Play, Move, and Have Fun!

Do you want to join the fun?"

Yes, I want to play and move!

No, not today.

Appendix D

Pre-Interview Questions (Educators' Attitudes and Knowledge on PE in Preschool Curriculum)

1. What is your understanding of the role of Physical Education (PE) in the preschool curriculum?
2. Do you currently incorporate structured physical exercise activities into your daily or weekly preschool routine? If so, what types of activities do you use?
3. In your experience, what are the main benefits of physical activity for preschool children, particularly in relation to their learning, social skills, and overall development?
4. Do you believe there are any challenges or barriers to effectively integrating physical exercise into the preschool curriculum? If so, what are they?

Interview Questions for Educators

1. Has your view of physical exercise in early childhood education changed after taking part in this program? If so, in what way?
2. Do you feel more confident and motivated to include physical activities in your daily preschool routine now? Why or why not?
3. Have you noticed any changes in how you approach physical activities with children since the program started? Could you share an example?
4. What kind of impact do you think this program had on the children? Have you seen any differences in their engagement, social interactions, or development?
5. Looking back, what do you think worked well in the program, and what could be improved to make it even more effective for both children and educators?
6. Do you see yourself continuing to use structured physical activities in your curriculum moving forward? What would help make that easier or more effective for you?

Appendix E

Instructions

1. Please note that this ethical approval application form must be completed with reference to and comply with *TUS Research Ethics Policy and Procedures for Undergraduate and Taught Programmes*. This template serves as a resource that may be adopted by the Project supervisor/Programme Board to suit a particular disciplinary area.
2. If you do not obtain ethical approval in writing from your research project supervisor your project may fail on ethical grounds.
3. Please complete all sections and submit this Application Form to your Research Project Supervisor.
4. Submit copies of any data collection instruments, information sheets and informed consent forms (outlining participants' right to withdraw with no negative consequences).

Student Name & Id Number	Kristina Rautek Potocnik K00326871
Department	Department of Sport & Early Childhood
Programme Title	Master of Arts in Early Intervention and Inclusive Practice for Children
Project Title	The Impact of Physical Exercise Interventions on Engagement and Responsiveness in Preschool Children
Supervisor Name	Helen Maher
Provide a clear and succinct research question. 'How does a physical exercise intervention impact the engagement and responsiveness of preschool children in an inclusive setting?'	
State the primary aim and any additional aims of the proposed research (the aims should be stated as clearly and succinctly as possible). Primary Aim: To examine how a physical exercise intervention influences the engagement and responsiveness of preschool children in an inclusive setting. Additional Aims: This study aims to explore how children's perspectives and reactions—such as direct feedback and observable responses—can be incorporated into the ongoing process of refining the intervention, while also examining educators' perceptions regarding the intervention's influence on children's behaviour and engagement. Additionally, it seeks to determine how inclusive practices are addressed and strengthened through continuous adaptations of the physical activity component.	
Method of data collection	<input type="checkbox"/> Survey <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Focus Group <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Interview <input type="checkbox"/> Content Analysis <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Participant Observer <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
Provide detail on the Method of Study Design (Include estimated number of participants). This study employs a qualitative, action research design to investigate how preschool children aged 3 to 4.5 years engage with a play-based physical exercise intervention, as well as to explore educators' perspectives on its implementation. Action research enables continuous evaluation and adjustment, making it particularly suitable for examining real-world educational practices and addressing the evolving needs of young learners. By focusing on naturalistic observation and reflective processes, this qualitative approach aims to capture the subtleties of children's responsiveness, the "voice" of the child in providing feedback, and the ways in which educators adapt their instructional strategies. In this study, "physical exercise" refers early years intervention that consist of a variety of structured physical activities, lasting between 15 and 40 minutes, depending on whether the session takes place in the classroom, playground, or hall. The program is designed to be developmentally appropriate, ensuring that activities are engaging, inclusive, and suitable for preschool-aged children.	

The intervention includes structured movement-based activities that aim to enhance motor skills, coordination, balance, and overall physical well-being, while also fostering social interaction and cognitive engagement. Activities will range from guided play, sensory-motor exercises, music and movement activities, action-based storytelling, and nature-based exploration, to cooperative movement games that promote inclusivity and support diverse developmental needs.

Through playful, interactive exercises—such as parachute games, rhythm-based movements, obstacle courses, and imaginative role-play that integrates movement—the intervention provides a holistic and engaging approach to physical activity within an inclusive preschool setting. The goal is to create a positive and supportive environment where all children can participate, develop essential movement skills, and benefit from the social and cognitive aspects of physical play.

An estimated 30 to 35 preschool children will participate in the study, divided into two groups to ensure manageable group sizes and facilitate individual observation. Additionally, four to six preschool educators will take part, providing their understanding and feedback on the intervention through pre- and post-interviews. These interviews will offer valuable qualitative insights into their perspectives on the intervention's impact on children's engagement, responsiveness, participation, and overall learning experiences in an inclusive preschool setting.

The study will integrate observational data, reflective journals, and educators feedback interview to provide a comprehensive understanding of how a movement-based play intervention supports children's engagement and responsiveness in preschool environments.

Does your proposed research need initial clearance from a 'gatekeeper' (e.g. local authority, head teacher, college head, nursery/playgroup manager)?

Yes - Preschool manager

No

If Yes, please provide details and indicate how you will negotiate this in your proposal?

During a meeting with the manager, it was agreed that I would conduct the research, provided I supply consent forms for parents and educators. In accordance with the TUS Ethics Policy, all research involving human participants must comply with the principles of informed consent, beneficence, confidentiality, and integrity to ensure ethical research practices (TUS MA Dissertation Handbook, 2024/5, p.15).

Are human participants required for the proposed research?

Yes

No

If Yes, please provide details and indicate how you will negotiate this in your proposal?

Yes, the study involves approximately 30 to 35 preschool children and four to six educators. To ensure ethical research practices and informed participation, comprehensive information sheets and consent forms will be provided to all participants, including parents, children, and educators.

Parents will receive a detailed information sheet outlining the purpose of the study, the nature of their child's participation, potential risks and benefits, confidentiality measures, and the right to withdraw at any time. The parental consent form will require their signed approval for their child's involvement in the research.

Since the participants are preschool-aged children (3–4.5 years), assent will be obtained in an age-appropriate manner. A simplified, child-friendly explanation of the activities will be provided through visual aids and verbal communication. Children will be informed that they can choose not to participate or stop at any time if they feel uncomfortable.

Educators participating in the study will be given a separate information sheet explaining their role in the research, including their observations, reflections, and possible interviews. The educator consent form will confirm their voluntary participation, the confidentiality of their responses, and their right to withdraw from the study without any consequences.

All consent and assent procedures will be designed in line with TUS Ethics Policy to ensure compliance with ethical research standards (Technological University of the Shannon, 2024, p. 15).

Does your proposed research involve work with 'vulnerable' populations?

Yes

No

Please explain your answer:

Yes, the study involves preschool children aged 3 to 4.5 years, who are considered a vulnerable population due to their young age and developing capacity for informed decision-making. As per the TUS Research Ethics Policy, research involving vulnerable participants requires special ethical considerations, including obtaining parental consent, child assent, maintaining confidentiality, and ensuring beneficence to protect their well-being (Technological University of the Shannon, 2023, p. 7). In line with these ethical standards, the study will incorporate detailed parental information sheets and consent forms, age-appropriate assent procedures for children, and educator consent forms, ensuring that all participants engage in the research voluntarily, with full understanding of their rights.

Are there any potential risks to participants or ethical concerns associated with the proposed research?

Yes

No

Please explain your answer:

Yes, there are minor risks associated with physical exercise (e.g., the possibility of slips or minor injuries) and potential emotional discomfort if children do not wish to participate. These risks may arise in each session of the intervention. To mitigate them, educators and the researcher will closely supervise activities, adapt the exercises in response to children's feedback, and allow any child who becomes distressed or uncomfortable to stop immediately. Parents and educators will also be fully informed of these potential risks in the consent forms, and procedures will be in place for promptly addressing any concerns that arise.

Please indicate how informed consent will be obtained from your participants? (Your consent letters/forms must inform participants that they have the right to withdraw from the study at any time).

Informed consent will be obtained by providing clearly written information sheets and consent forms to both parents (on behalf of their children) and educators. These forms will explicitly state that participation is voluntary and that they may withdraw at any time without penalty. Additionally, since the study involves preschool-aged children, age-appropriate assent procedures will be implemented. Children will be provided with a simple verbal explanation of the study using visual aids and interactive communication strategies

Have you ensured (in your consent form) that participants are aware of who they should contact if they have a complaint?

Yes

No

Please explain:

Informed consent will be obtained by providing clearly written information sheets and consent forms to both parents (on behalf of their children) and educators. These forms will explicitly state that participation is voluntary and that they may withdraw at any time without penalty. Additionally, since the study involves preschool-aged children, age-appropriate assent procedures will be implemented. Children will be provided with a simple verbal explanation of the study using visual aids and interactive communication strategies to ensure they understand their right to say yes or no to participation.

Furthermore, the contact details of the research supervisor will be provided on the information sheets and consent forms to ensure that participants have a point of contact should they have any concerns or wish to make a complaint regarding the study.

Please attach your Consent Forms to this application (if relevant).

Please explain your debriefing procedures (if relevant).

A short, age-appropriate explanation of the study's purpose and outcomes will be shared with the children in a way they can understand, while educators and parents will receive a more detailed summary of the findings.

This ensures transparency, gives participants the opportunity to discuss any questions they may have, and highlights how their contributions informed the research.

Are you proposing to collect video and/or audio data?

- Yes
 No

If Yes, please explain, how you will protect participants' anonymity and confidentiality
Please explain, how you will store the data?

This study involves audio recording of interviews with educators to ensure accuracy in transcription and analysis. No video recording will take place. To protect participants' anonymity and confidentiality, pseudonyms will be assigned, and all identifying information will be removed from transcripts. Audio recordings will be securely stored on an encrypted, password-protected device with access limited to the researcher and their institutional supervisor. In line with TUS Research Ethics Policy, all data will be handled in accordance with ethical and legal requirements for data protection, ensuring participant privacy is maintained at all times (Technological University of the Shannon, 2023, p. 7).

All research data, including audio recordings, transcripts, and consent forms, will be securely stored in compliance with TUS data management policies. Audio files will be encrypted and stored on a password-protected institutional cloud service, with restricted access to the researcher and supervisor. Written transcripts will be stored separately from audio files to further ensure confidentiality. Data will be retained for the minimum required period, as per TUS Data Retention Policy, after which all files will be permanently deleted after 7 years (Technological University of the Shannon, 2023, p. 23).

Have you built in time for a pilot study ?

(A pilot study may help ensure that any task materials you propose to use are appropriate and that they are unlikely to cause offence to any of your participants?)

- Yes
 No

Please explain your answer:

Yes. A short pilot study will be conducted with a small subset of children to test the appropriateness of the physical activities, ensure no offence is caused, and allow for any necessary adjustments before the main study begins.

Is your research likely to involve discussion of sensitive topics ?

(e.g. adult/child relationships, peer relationships, discussions about personal teaching styles, ability levels of individual children and/or adults)

- Yes
 No

If yes, what safeguards have you put in place to protect participants' confidentiality?

Since the study may involve discussions of children's abilities and educators' reflections on personal teaching styles, all data will be anonymised. Participant identities will be protected through the use of pseudonyms, and any potentially identifying details will be omitted from all written and verbal reports to safeguard confidentiality. Additionally, while every effort will be made to ensure anonymity, it is acknowledged that there is always a possibility that children may disclose sensitive issues during interactions. In such cases, established school policies and safeguarding procedures will be followed to address any concerns with sensitivity and in accordance with ethical guidelines.

Does your proposed research raise any issues of personal safety for yourself or other persons involved in the project?

Yes

No

If Yes, please provide details.

How do you propose to ensure your own safety and that of your participants?

Yes, the research involves minor safety considerations as it includes working with preschool children and educators during play-based physical activities and conducting in-person observations and interviews. The primary concerns relate to ensuring a safe environment for children during movement-based activities, maintaining appropriate supervision, and ensuring the researcher's well-being during data collection.

To ensure the safety of all participants, a preliminary risk assessment will be conducted to identify and mitigate potential hazards associated with physical activities. Play-based exercises will take place in a safe and supervised environment under the guidance of preschool staff. The researcher will only observe or interact with children in the presence of qualified educators to ensure appropriate supervision and minimize risks. The study will adhere strictly to the TUS Research Ethics Policy, ensuring compliance with child protection policies, informed consent procedures, and confidentiality guidelines (Technological University of the Shannon, 2023, p. 10).

Interviews with educators will be conducted in secure, professional settings such as school premises or designated meeting rooms to ensure both researcher and participant safety. All data, including audio recordings and transcripts, will be securely stored and anonymized in compliance with TUS data management policies (Technological University of the Shannon, 2023, p. 23). The researcher will also familiarize themselves with the preschool's emergency protocols and will have access to first aid support if required. These measures ensure that all aspects of the research are conducted in a safe, ethical, and professional manner, prioritizing the well-being of children, educators, and the researcher.

Do you have the name of an appropriate mental health professional or organisation available if a participant becomes distressed because of participation in the research process and needs to access support?

Yes

No

If Yes, please provide details.

Rowe Creavin Medical Practice

Have you attached a copy of any stimulus materials e.g. questionnaires /interview schedule etc.?

Please select here and submit accordingly.

	Electronic Copy	Hard Copy	N/A
Pre-Participation Questionnaire	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
PAR-Q	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Participant Recruitment Email	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Participant Recruitment Poster	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Participant Information Sheet	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Parental/Guardian Information Sheet	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Informed Consent Form	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Parental Consent Form	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Permission Letters/E-mails	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Children assent form	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Relevant Information Sheet(s)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Interview questions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Note: All accompanying documentation must be collated and included at the end of this word document.

Student Declaration:

I understand that it is my responsibility to inform my supervisor fully and honestly of all details relating to the conduct of the study and to follow the direction of my supervisor and of the research ethics panel. I understand that it is my responsibility to obtain approval for the study prior to the commencement of the study and to follow approved procedures at all times.

X

Signature of Student

Official Use Only

Please select as appropriate

Approved

Not Approved

In not approved please provide relevant feedback:

x
Dr. Helen Maher

Signature of Project Supervisor or
Chair Research Ethics Panel

Date: 24/ 02 / 2025